

Checklist of sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) from Iran

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ABSTRACT. An updated list of the sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) from Iran is provided. The list includes 178 species of sawflies belonging to 60 genera and 9 families. Family Tenthredinidae is the most species-rich group (131 species) followed by Argidae (18 species), Cephidae (9 species), Megalodontesidae (7 species), Cimbicidae (4 species), Pamphiliidae (3 species), Orussidae, Siricidae and Xiphydriidae (each with 2 species). Also genus *Tenthredo* is the most species-rich genus with 23 species followed by *Macrophya* (Tenthredinidae) with 17 species and *Arge* (Argidae) with 12 species. General distribution, synonyms and hosts associated with larvae for all recorded species are provided.

Key words: Hymenoptera, Symphyta, checklist, distribution, Iran

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Introduction

Sawfly is the common name for insects belong to “Symphyta” (Insecta: Hymenoptera), comprising 14 families. Sawflies are recognizable from the other hymenopterans by broad connection between the abdomen and the thorax, a pair of metanotal protuberances (except the Cephidae), the cenchri, and by their caterpillar-like larvae (Quinlan & Gauld 1981, Smith 1988). The common name comes from the saw-like of the ovipositor, which the females use to lay their eggs into the plants. Females of Siricidae (with common name of horntails) have long slender ovipositors for depositing eggs in wood. Large populations of some sawfly species can cause considerable economic

damage to agricultural crops, ornamental plants, and forests. In fact sawflies are a large group of herbivorous insects except Orussidae. Most specialists on the taxonomy of Symphyta believe that the nearest taxon to the Apocrita is the Orussidae, the only symphytan group which is parasitic (Smith, 1988; Viitasaari, 2002). The sawflies larvae live often on or sometimes in various plants, and some of them are attracted to one specific group of plants. Mostly they are feeding freely on the surface of leaves but some species make mines in the leaves or twigs of different plants (Viitasaari, 2002).

Some species of sawflies are potential economic pests (Quinlan & Gauld, 1981). For example, *Hoplocampa flava* (Linnaeus,

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1760) and *H. minuta* (Christ, 1791) are the important pests of plums and prunes. Amount of damage by *H. flava* on plums is about 40% around the Karaj city (Davoudi, 1995). *Arge ochropus* (Gmelin, 1790) has regarded as an important pest on *Rosa* spp. in northern Iran (Farahbakhsh 1961, Abai 2009, Sahragard & Heydari, 2001). Amount of damage by *Cephus pygmeus* (Linnaeus, 1767) on wheat is determined to be 25% in Varamin region (Ghadiri, 1993).

About 1350 sawfly species from Tenthredinidae (almost 116 from Allantinae; 77 from Blennocampinae; 62 from Heterarthrinae; 618 from Nematinae; 126 from Selandriinae and 345 from Tenthredininae) and nearly 440 species from other families of sawflies are distributed in the West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010). According to literature, (Abai, 2009; Abai & Moghadam, 1993; Beneš, 1981; Beneš & Abai, 1991; Benson, 1968; Chevin, 1985; Ebrahimi, 1995; Farahbakhsh, 1961; Gussakovskij, 1935; Khayrandish et al., in press, 2015; Koch, 1988; Lacourt, 1999; Mallach, 1931; Modarres Awal, 1997; Shahmohammadi et al., 2008; Shinohara, 1997; Taeger, 2002; Taeger & Blank, 2011; Wei, 2008; Zirngiebl, 1956) 178 sawfly species have been recorded from Iran. Major faunistic works were contributed by Mallach (1931), Zirngiebl (1956), Benson (1968), Chevin (1985) and Khayrandish et al. (2015, in press). Tenthredinidae and Argidae comprise about 73.5% and 10% of the known Iranian sawflies, respectively.

By reviewing the published data, this work provides a first list of all the sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) from Iran. This study will be a valuable tool for future studies on biodiversity, ecology and integrated pest management.

Material and methods

The published data on the sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) are summarized.

Names of the valid genera and species are listed alphabetically within the families. Valid taxa names, published records within provincial distribution (Fig. 1), general distribution and host records are provided.

Results

I- Family Argidae

1- *Aprosthemella melanurum* (Klug, 1814)

Synonyms: *Hylotoma melanura* Klug, 1814: 303–304; *Schizocera cylindricornis* Thomson, 1871: 44–45; *Schizocera alfkeni* Konow, 1895: 72–73; *Schizocera friesei* Konow, 1895: 73–74.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Lathyrus pratensis* Linnaeus, *L. tuberosus* Linnaeus (Fabaceae) and *Vicia cracca* Linnaeus (Fabaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

Remarks: Benson (1968) listed Iran under the general distribution of *A. melanurum* but he did not present detailed collection data for this country. So occurrence of this species in Iran need to be re-confirmed.

2- *Aprosthemella tardum* (Klug, 1814)

Synonyms: *Hylotoma tarda* Klug, 1814: 304; *Aprosthemella carpentieri* Konow, 1902b: 386–387.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Figure 1. Geographic map of provinces in Iran.

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Lathyrus* spp. (Fabaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

Remarks: Benson (1968) listed Iran under the general distribution of *A. tardum* but he did not present detailed collection data for this country. So occurrence of this species in Iran need to be re-confirmed.

3- *Arge berberidis* Schrank, 1802

Synonyms: *Tenthredo xanthopyga* Vallot, 1836: 212–213.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press) and

Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Liston, 1995).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagous feeding on *Berberis sieboldi* Miquel, B.

thunbergi De Candolle, *B. vulgaris* Linnaeus and *Mahonia aquifolium* (Pursh) (Berberidaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

4- *Arge cingulata* (Jakowlew, 1891)

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Muche, 1977; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: East Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010), Iran, Tajikistan, Turkestan and Uzbekistan (Ushinskij, 1936; Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Unknown.

5- *Arge cyanocrocea* (Forster, 1771)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo cyanocrocea* Forster, 1771: 78; *Tenthredo coerulea* Fabricius, 1775: 321; *Tenthredo bicolor* Schrank, 1776: 84; *Hylotoma syriaca* Mocsáry, 1880: 267; *Hylotoma cyanocrocea* var. *messanensis* De-Stefani, 1885: 185; *Hylotoma syriaca* var. *damascena* Magretti, 1890: 525; *Arge cyanocrocea* forma *afasciata* Ermolenko, 1975: 43.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968); Northern of Iran (Ushinskij, 1936); Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press); Lorestan (Mallach, 1931) and Mazandaran (Mallach, 1931; Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Liston, 1995).

Host plants: Larvae feed on ?*Rubus* Linnaeus and *Sanguisorba officinalis* Linnaeus (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

6- *Arge enodis* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo enodis* Linné, 1767: 922; *Tenthredo violacea* Fabricius, 1779: 64;

Tenthredo coeruleipennis Retzius, 1783: 72; *Hylotoma atrata* Klug, 1814: 286–287; *Hylotoma amethystina* Klug, 1814: 31; *Hylotoma vulgaris* Klug, 1834: 230.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Farahbakhsh, 1961); Northern of Iran (Dadurian, 1962; Behdad, 1988).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagous feeding on *Salix alba* Linnaeus, *S. fragilis* Linnaeus, *S. purpurea* Linnaeus, *S. babylonica* Linnaeus (Salicaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

7- *Arge impressifrons* Konow, 1898

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan (Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Iran (Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Unknown.

8- *Arge melanochra* (Gmelin, 1790)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo melanochra* Gmelin, 1790: 2657; *Hylotoma femoralis* Klug, 1814: 295–296; *Hylotoma dimidiata* Lepeletier, 1823: 43; *Hylotoma dimidiata* Serville, 1823: 12–13; *Hylotoma nigratarsis* Klug, 1834: 233; *Hylotoma similis* Rudow, 1871: 384; *Arge fuliginata* Konow, 1907: 489; *Arge melanochra* forma *marginatopropodea* Ermolenko, 1975: 41; *Arge melanochra* forma *nigropropodea* Ermolenko, 1975: 41.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968); Caspian coast (Mallach, 1931); Alborz, Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press) Gilan, Mazandaran (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press) and Golestan (Muche, 1977) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Liston, 1995).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Crataegus laevigata* Poiret (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

9- *Arge nigripes* (Retzius, 1783)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo nigripes* Retzius, 1783: 71; *Hylotoma hartigi* Konow, 1885c: 117; *Arge annulata* Konow, 1891: 42.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Azerbaijan, France, Germany, Greece, Iran, Russia and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Fragaria* and *Rosa* (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

10- *Arge ochropus* (Gmelin, 1790)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo ochropus* Gmelin, 1790: 2657; *Arge rosincola* Schrank, 1802: 228–229; *Hylotoma rosarum* Klug, 1814: 292–293; *Hylotoma pyrenaica* André, 1879: 48; *Arge soror* Konow, 1890b: 8; *Arge pyrenaica* var. *nigripes* Konow, 1895: 71; *Arge modesta* Konow, 1905b: 157; *Arge pyrenaicamauritanica* Schulz, 1906: 85; *Hylotoma rosae* var. *diversicolor* Pic, 1917: 19; *Arge pyrenaica luteola* Mucho, 1977: II, 31.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009); Alborz (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press); East Azerbaijan (Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936; Chevin, 1985); Fars (Abai, 2009); Gilan (Sahragard & Heydari, 2001; Khayrandish et al., in press); Golestan (Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936) and

Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Liston, 1995).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagous feeding on *Rosa canina* Linnaeus, *R. gallica* Linnaeus, *R. rubiginosa* Linnaeus, *R. majalis* Herrmann and *R. pimpinellifolia* Linnaeus (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

11- *Arge persica* Gussakovskij, 1935

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Gussakovskij, 1935; Benson, 1968; Mucho, 1977).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

12- *Arge rustica* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo rustica* Linnaeus, 1758: 556; *Tenthredo atrata* Forster, 1771: 80; *Cryptus segmentarius* Panzer, 1803: 88: 17; *Hylotoma klugii* Leach, 1817: 122–123; *Hylotoma leachii* Stephens, 1829: 326; *Hylotoma albicruris* Brullé, 1832: 395; *Hylotoma leachii* Stephens, 1835: 17; *Hylotoma marginata* Boheman, 1852: 170–171; *Hylotoma discus* Costa, 1858: 17, 26; *Hylotoma saliceti* Rudow, 1871: 383; *Hylotoma Thomsoni* Konow, 1884: 309; *Arge segmentaria* var. *rufiventris* Konow, 1899: 204.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria,

Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Alnus* Miller (Betulaceae); *Quercus robur* Linnaeus (Fagaceae); *Salix* Linnaeus (Salicaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

13- *Arge scita* (Mocsáry, 1880)

Synonyms: *Hylotoma scita* Mocsáry, 1880: 267; *Hylotoma proxima* André, 1881a: 347–348; *Arge debilis* Konow, 1887a: 19–20; *Arge zarudnii* Gussakovskij, 1935: 259, 417–418.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Muche, 1969, 1977); Southeast of Iran (Gussakovskij, 1935); Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece, Iran, Jordan, Lebanon, Russia, Turkey and Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

14- *Arge simulatrix* Konow, 1887

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Bulgaria, Greece, Russia, Syria and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

15- *Kokujewia ectrapela* Konow, 1902

Synonym: *Kokujewia ectrapela* var. *clarescens* Zirngiebl, 1949: 284.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Karimpour & Razmi, 2010); West Azerbaijan (Karimpour, 2007a, 2007b); East Azerbaijan and Lorestan (Taeger & Blank, 2011) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Azerbaijan,

Georgia, Iran and Russia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Romex* spp. (Polygonaceae) (Karimpour, 2015; Karimpour & Razmi, 2010).

16- *Sterictiphora angelicae* (Panzer, 1799)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo angelicae* Panzer, 1799: 72: 1; *Tenthredo taraxaci* Panzer, 1806: 24; *Cryptus villersii* Leach, 1817: 124–125; *Schizoceros henschi* Konow, 1907: 492.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Koch, 1988); Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus* spp. (Taeger et al., 1998).

17- *Sterictiphora caspica* Koch, 1988

Distribution in Iran: Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Koch, 1988; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Koch, 1988; Taeger & Blank, 2011; Khayrandish et al., in press).

Host plants: Unknown.

18- *Sterictiphora furcata* (Villers, 1789)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo furcata* Villers, 1789: 86–87; *Tenthredo rubi idaei* Rossi, 1790: vol. 2, 31; *Schizocera inaequalis* Bremi-Wolf, 1849: 94–95; *Aprosthemata terebralis* var. *flavipes* Enslin, 1917: 618.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Muche, 1977); Mazandaran province (Chevin, 1985).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Italy, Jordan, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Portugal,

Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus idaeus* (Linnaeus) and *Prunus spinosa* Linnaeus (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

II- Family Cephidae

19- *Calameuta (Calameuta) filiformis* (Eversmann, 1847)

Synonym: *Cephus quadricinctus* Dahlbom, 1835a: 15; *Cephus filiformis* Eversmann, 1847: 64; *Cephus elongates* Snellen van Vollenhoven, 1858a: 280–281; *Cephus arundinis* Giraud, 1863: 1286; *Cephus marginatus* Kawall, 1864: 301–302; *Cephus erberi* Damianitsch, 1866: 994; *Cephus vagabundus* Mocsáry, 1886b: 102–103; *Cephus infernalis* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1926: 129–130; *Calameuta atrata* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1931: 42–43; *Calameuta rugose* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1931: 42–43; *Calameuta amurensis* Gussakovskij, 1935: 97–98, 354–355.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Dadurian, 1962; Klima, 1937); East Azerbaijan (Gussakovskij, 1935) and Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Caucasus and Iran (Gussakovskij, 1935).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Phragmites australis* (Cavanilles) *Phalaris arundinacea* Linnaeus, *Arrhenatherum elatius* (Linnaeus), *Elytrigia repens* (Linnaeus) and *Calamagrostis epigejos* (Linnaeus) (Poaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

20- *Calameuta (Calameuta) grombczewskii* (Jakowlew, 1891)

Synonym: *Cephus grombczewskii* Jakowlew, 1891: 13.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Qazvin, Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Golestan (Taeger & Blank, 2011) provinces.

General distribution: East Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan (Ushinskij, 1936).

Host plants: Unknown.

21- *Calameuta (Calameuta) idolon* (Rossi, 1794)

Synonyms: *Ichneumon idolon* Rossi, 1794: 110; *Cephus mittrei* Guérin, 1844: 402; *Cephus bellieri* Sichel, 1860: 757; *Cephus variegatus* J.P.E.F. Stein, 1876: 59–60; *Monoplopus apicicornis* Pic, 1916: 24.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968); Gilan and Qazvin provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Portugal, Spain, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

22- *Cephus nigrinus* Thomson, 1871

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Milium effusum* Linnaeus and *Poa pratensis* Linnaeus (Poaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

23- *Cephus pygmeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Synonyms: *Sirex pygmeus* Linnaeus, 1767: 929–930; *Tenthredo polygona* Gmelin, 1790: 2670–2671; *Banchus viridator* Fabricius, 1804: 127–128; *Cephus subcylindricus* Gravenhorst, 1807: 274; *Cephus leskii* Lepeletier, 1823: 20; *Cephus flavisternum* Costa, 1882: 198–199; *Cephus clypealis* Costa, 1894: 250; *Cephus pygmaeus* var. *palaestinus* Pic, 1918: 2; *Cephus tanaiticus* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1926: 131.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936);

Dadurian, 1962; Benson, 1965, 1968); Alborz, Tehran and probably northern and central provinces (Farahbakhsh, 1961); Tehran province (Behdad, 1982); Golestan province (Chevin, 1985); Alborz, Tehran and so northern and central provinces (Esmaili et al., 1991); Alborz, Markazi and Tehran provinces (Ghadiri, 1993, 1994a, 1994b, 2000); Tehran, Markazi and probably other northern and central provinces (Modarres Awal, 1997); Ghadiri and Irani (1999); Ghadiri and Safai (2001); Taeger and Blank (2011); Alborz, Qazvin and Tehran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Widely distributed in Palaearctic; Algeria and Egypt in Africa (Taeger & Blank, 2011), introduced to North America (Middlekauff, 1969).

Host plants: Associated with several Poaceae, sometimes regarded as a pest of crops for example *Avena sativa* Linnaeus, *Bromus secalinus* Linnaeus, *Hordeum vulgare* Linnaeus, *Secale cereale* Linnaeus and *Triticum aestivum* Linnaeus (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Middlekauff, 1969; Ghadiri, 1993; Modarres Awal, 1997). *Lepidium draba* Linnaeus, *Sysimbrium sophia* Linnaeus, (Brassicaceae), *Lisaea heterocarpa* Boissier (Apiaceae) and *Euphorbia heterophylla* Linnaeus (Euphorbiaceae) are cited as hosts by Modarres Awal (1997) but these data supposedly refer to flowers visit by adults.

24- *Hartigia nr xanthostoma* (Eversmann, 1847)

Synonyms: *Cephus xanthostoma* Eversmann, 1847: 63; *Cerobactrus facialis* Costa, 1864: 104; *Macrocephus ulmariae* Schlechtendal, 1878: 153-154; *Phyllaecus giraudi* Schlechtendal, 1880: 189; *Hartigia semenovi* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1931: 40-41; *Hartigia jakovlevi* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1931: 40-41.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Gilan provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic,

Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

25- *Pachycephus smyrnensis persicus* Gussakovskij, 1935

Synonyms: *Pachycephus persicus* Gussakovskij, 1935: 81, 347-348.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Scheibelreiter, 1978); Lorestan province (Gussakovskij, 1935; Benson, 1968);

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan, Iran, Lebanon and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

26- *Syrista parreyssii* (Spinola, 1843)

Synonyms: *Cephus parreyssii* Spinola, 1843: 116-117; *Cephus orientalis* Tischbein, 1852a: 139; *Cephus spectabilis* J.P.E.F. Stein, 1876: 58-59; *Macrocephus robustus* Mocsáry, 1883: 9-10; *Cephus parreyssi* var. *rufiventris* Jakowlew, 1888: 372.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Wei & Smith, 2010; Taeger & Blank, 2011); Northern provinces (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009); Alborz (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press); Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press); Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press); South Khorasan (Shahrokhi & Zare, 1995; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009) and Tehran (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Chevin, 1985; Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Iran, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Macedonia, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey, Turkmenistan and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Wei, 2008; Wei & Smith, 2010).

Host plants: The larvae bore into the stems of *Rosa* species (Wei & Smith, 2010); Larvae of *Syrista parreyssii* attack to newly grown twigs of *Berberis* (Shahrokhi & Zare, 1995).

27- *Trachelus tabidus* (Fabricius, 1775)

Synonyms: *Sirex tabidus* Fabricius, 1775: 326; *Sirex macilentus* Fabricius, 1793: 131; *Cephus mandibularis* Lepeletier, 1823: 20; *Cephus nigrinus* Lepeletier, 1823: 20; *Cephus mandibularis* Serville, 1823; *Cephus nigrinus* Serville, 1823: 96; *Cephus vittatus* Costa, 1875: 14; *Calamenta johnsoni* Ashmead, 1900: 600; *Calameuta johnsonii* Ashmead, 1903: 233; *Trachelus tabidus* var. *atrioventris* Pic, 1920: 14.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1982); Fars (Khalaf, 1995; Modarres Awal, 1997); Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Tehran (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1982; Modarres Awal, 1997; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Libya, Morocco, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011); introduced in the U.S.A (Gahan, 1920).

Host plants: Larvae feed on various grains such as *Triticum aestivum*, *Hordeum vulgare*, *Secale cereale*, *Avena sativa* and various wild grasses (Gussakovskij, 1935; Berland, 1941; Benson, 1951; Farahbakhsh, 1961; Middlekauff, 1969; Burggraaf-Van Nierop & Achterberg, 1990; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Modarres Awal, 1997). *Hordeum* Linnaeus, *Avena* Linnaeus, *Secale* Linnaeus, *Triticum* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998).

III- Family Cimbicidae

28- *Abia sericea* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo sericea* Linnaeus, 1767: 921; *Abia dorsalis* Costa, 1859b: 5-6.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Dadurian, 1962); Lorestan, Mazandaran (Mallach, 1931) and Gilan (Ebrahimi, 1995) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Succisa pratensis* Moench and *Knautia arvensis* (Linnaeus) (Caprifoliaceae); *Fragaria* (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

29- *Cimbex femoratus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo femorata* Linnaeus, 1758: 555; *Tenthredo tristis* Fabricius, 1779: 334; *Crabro lunulatus* Geoffroy, 1785: 362; *Crabro annulatus* Geoffroy, 1785: 362; *Tenthredo sylvarum* Fabricius, 1793: 105-106; *Cimbex europaea* Leach, 1817: 104; *Cimbex varians* Leach, 1817: 105; *Cimbex variabilis* Klug, 1820: 72; *Tenthredo russa* Klug, 1820: 79; *Cimbex schaefferi* Lepeletier, 1823: 26; *Cimbex pallens* Lepeletier, 1823: 28-30; *Cimbex schaefferi* Serville, 1823: 3; *Cimbex pallens* Serville, 1823: 5; *Cimbex pallidus* Stephens, 1829: 324; *Cimbex venusta* Perty, 1833: 129; *Cimbex biguetina* Lepeletier, 1834: 455; *Cimbex pallida* Stephens, 1835: 7; *Cimbex betulae* Zaddach, 1863: 249; *Cimbex betulae* var. *pulla* Zaddach, 1863: 250; *Cimbex betulae* var. *feminae flavo-maculata* Zaddach, 1863: 251; *Cimbex betulae* var. *feminae lutescens* Zaddach, 1863: 251; *Cimbex betulae* var. *nigra* Zaddach, 1863: 250; *Cimbex tonnaitchana* Matsumura, 1911: 86; *Cimbex femorata* var. *unicolor* Enslin, 1917: 569; *Cimbex femorata* var. *abdominalis* Enslin, 1917: 569; *Cimbex femorata* var. *ornata* Uchida, 1927: 159; *Cimbex quadrimaculata* var. *sachalinensis* Uchida, 1927: 161; *Crabro uchidai* Takeuchi, 1931: 19.

Distribution in Iran: Tehran province (Abai, 2009).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Korea (North and South Korea), Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Betula pubescens* Ehrhart and *B. pendula* Roth (Taeger et al., 1998).

30- *Corynis caucasica* (Moscary, 1886)

Synonyms: *Amasis Caucasica* Mocsáry, 1886a: 2-3; *Amasis caspica* Konow, 1886c: 37-38.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Muche, 1972); Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Bulgaria and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Southeast of Europe, Turkey, Transcaucasia and Iran (Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Unknown.

31- *Corynis obscura* (Fabricius, 1775)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo obscura* Fabricius, 1775: 319; *Amasis helvetica* Konow, 1886c: 37-38; *Amasis obscura* var. *adusta* Zirngiebl, 1953: 235; *Amasis valkanovi* Vassilev, 1969: 695-696.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Gussakovskij, 1935; Muche, 1973).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al. 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

IV- Family Megalodontesidae

32- *Megalodontes escaleraei* Konow, 1899

Distribution in Iran: West Azerbaijan province (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Lebanon, Syria and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

33- *Megalodontes eversmanni* (Freymuth, 1870)

Synonyms: *Tarpa eversmanni* Freymuth, 1870: 225; *Tarpa loewii* J.P.E.F. Stein, 1876: 56-57; *Tarpa (Megalodontes) multicincta* Mocsáry, 1891: 157-158.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger, 2002), Qazvin and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Georgia, Greece, Iran, Russia, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger, 2002; Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

34- *Megalodontes flavicornis* (Klug, 1824)

Synonym: *Tarpa flavicornis* Klug, 1824: 192-193.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Taeger, 2002); East Azerbaijan (Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936) and Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Russia, Slovakia, Turkey, Turkmenistan and Ukraine (Taeger, 2002; Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

35- *Megalodontes guichardi* Springate, Burckhardt and Springate, 2011

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: North Africa and Middle East (Springate et al., 2011); Iraq, Israel, Syria and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

36- *Megalodontes olivieri* (Brullé, 1846)

Synonym: *Tarpa olivieri* Brullé, 1846: 660.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Ebrahimi, 1995).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Morocco and Saudi Arabia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

37- *Megalodontes phaenicius* (Lepeletier, 1823)

Synonyms: *Tarpa phaenicia* Lepeletier, 1823: 15; *Tarpa caucasica* André, 1881d: 479; *Megalodontes* (*Rhipidioceros*) *imperialis* Konow, 1897b: 3; *Megalodontes* (*Rhipidioceros*) *kohli* Konow, 1897b: 3.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger, 2002); Sistan and Baluchestan province (Zirngiebl, 1956).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Egypt, Greece, Iran, Moldova, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

38- *Megalodontes xanthosomus* Zhelochovtsev, 1927

Synonym: *Megalodontes* (*Rhipidioceros*) *curticornis* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1930: 81–82.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936).

General distribution: East Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Iran (Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936).

Host plants: Unknown.

V- Family Orussidae

39- *Orussus abietinus* (Scopoli, 1763)

Synonyms: *Sphex abietina* Scopoli, 1763: 296; *Tenthredo degener* Christ, 1791: 438–439;

Sirex vespertilio Fabricius, 1793: 129; *Oryssus coronatus* Fabricius, 1798: 218; *Oryssus albopunctatus* Gimmerthal, 1836: 434; *Oryssus hyalinipennis* Costa, 1860: 4–5.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Kraus, 1998).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Algeria, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

40- *Pseudoryssus henschii* (Mocsáry, 1910)

Synonyms: *Oryssus henschii* Mocsáry, 1910: 161–162; *Pseudoryssus emanuelis* Guiglia, 1956: 24–25.

Distribution in Iran: Lorestan and Fars provinces (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Algeria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Germany, Greece, Iran, Iraq, Italy, Morocco, Russia, Switzerland, Turkey and Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

VI- Family Pamphiliidae

41- *Kelidoptera maculipennis* (J.P.E.F. Stein, 1876)

Synonym: *Lyda maculipennis* J.P.E.F. Stein, 1876: 57.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Shinohara, 2002).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Israel, Syria and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Iran (Shinohara, 2002).

Host plants: Unknown.

42- *Onycholyda trigaria* (Konow, 1897)

Synonym: *Pamphilius trigarius* Konow, 1897a: 242, 247–248.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Blank et al., 1998); Alborz (Khayrandish et al., in press); Gilan

(Shinohara, 1997, 2002; Khayrandish et al., in press) and Lorestan (Shinohara, 1997, 2002) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran and Russia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

43- *Pamphilius pallipes* (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Synonyms: *Lyda pallipes* Zetterstedt, 1838: 355; *Lyda flavipes* Zetterstedt, 1838: 355; *Lyda variegata* Zaddach, 1866: 161-162; *Pamphilius pallidipes* Dalla Torre, 1894: 435.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Shinohara, 2005).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Alnus viridis* De Candolle; *A. maximowiczii* Callier (Betulaceae); *Betula pendula* Roth and *B. pubescens* Ehrhart (Betulaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

VII- Family Siricidae

44- *Tremex fuscicornis* (Fabricius, 1787)

Synonyms: *Sirex fuscicornis* Fabricius, 1787: 257; *Sirex struthiocamelus* Villers, 1789: 132-133; *Sirex camelogigas* Christ, 1791: 411.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz (Shahmohammadi et al., 2008) and Razavi Khorasan (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic, Oriental and Neotropic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Bulgaria, Chile, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea (North and South Korea), Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are polyphagous feeding on *Acer* Linnaeus (Aceraceae), *Salix*, *Picea* Miller (Pinaceae), *Ulmus* Linnaeus (Ulmaceae), *Robinia* Linnaeus (Fabaceae) and *Juglans regia* Linnaeus (Juglandaceae) (Shahmohammadi et al. 2008); *Prunus x yedoensis* Matsumura (Rosaceae), *Ulmus propinqua* Koidzumi and *Zelkova serrata* (Thunberg) (Ulmaceae), *Acer negundo* Linnaeus, *Alnus japonica* (Thunberg), *Betula* and *Carpinus betulus* Linnaeus (Betulaceae), *Celtis sinensis* Persoon (Cannabaceae), *Quercus* Linnaeus and *Fagus sylvatica* Linnaeus (Fagaceae), *Salix* and *Populus tremula* Linnaeus (Salicaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

45- *Urocerus sah* (Mocsáry, 1881)

Synonym: *Sirex sah* Mocsáry, 1881: 36.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Mocsáry, 1881); Northern of Iran (Gussakovskij, 1935; Benson, 1943, 1968); Northern provinces (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Afghanistan, Iran, Russia, Spain, Turkey, Ukraine, USA and Uzbekistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Populus* and probably on *Ulmus* (Modarres Awal, 1997).

VIII- Family Tenthredinidae

Subfamily Allantinae

46- *Allantus (Emphytus) alborzanus* Khayrandish, Talebi & Blank

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Gilan provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Iran (Khayrandish et al., in press).

Host plants: Unknown.

47- *Allantus (Emphytus) cinctus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo cincta* Linnaeus, 1758: 557; *Tenthredo cordigera* Geoffroy, 1785: 374-375; *Dolerus cinctus* Jurine, 1807: pl. 6; *Dolerus (Emphytus) varipes* Lepeletier, 1823: 119; *Dolerus cingulatus* Serville, 1823: 54-55; *Dolerus varipes* Serville, 1823: 56; *Emphytus*

neglectus Zaddach, 1859: 27; *Emphytus cinctipes* Norton, 1867b: 229; *Emphytus infasciatus* Pic, 1948a: 11.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Korea (North and South Korea), Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Smith, 1979).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa pimpinellifolia* Linnaeus and *Fragaria* Linnaeus but other species of *Rosa* and *Rubus* are not confirmed (Taeger et al., 1998), *Rosa* (Liston & Späth, 2005).

48- *Allantus (Emphytus) cingulatus* (Scopoli, 1763)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo cingulata* Scopoli, 1763: 277; *Dolerus (Emphytus) cingulatus* Lepeletier, 1823: 117; *Tenthredo tenuis* Lepeletier, 1823: 128; *Emphytus elegans* Costa, 1859a: 38-39; *Allantus cingulatus* var. *muliebris* Enslin, 1914c: 229.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Fragaria ananassa* Duchesne (Rosaceae) and *Rosa canina* Linnaeus (Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993); *Fragaria* and *Rosa* (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1952; Lacourt, 1999); *Rosa*,

Corylus and *Betula* (Liston, 1995). Larvae of *Allantus cingulatus* have not been found on *Corylus* and *Betula* to now (Taeger et al., 1998).

49- *Allantus (Emphytus) didymus* (Klug, 1818)

Synonym: *Tenthredo (Emphytus) didyma* Klug, 1818: 282-283.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Qazvin, Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Greece (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Iran and Turkey (Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa* (Berland, 1947; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995); *Sanguisorba minor* Scopoli, *Rosa* spp. and *Rubus* spp. (Lacourt, 1999); *S. minor* (Liston, 2004); *Rosa* spp. and *Rubus* spp. are not confirmed as hosts (Taeger et al., 1998).

50- *Allantus (Emphytus) geminus* (Konow, 1891)

Synonym: *Emphytus geminus* Konow, 1891: 43-44.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011)

Host plants: Unknown.

51- *Allantus (Emphytus) koschevnikovi* (Konow, 1905)

Synonym: *Emphytus koschevnikovi* Konow, 1905b: 163.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Konow, 1905; Lacourt, 1999); Tehran province (Ushinskij, 1936; Zhelochovtsev, 1976).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran and Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

52- *Allantus (Emphytus) laticinctus* (Serville, 1823)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Emphytus) balteata* Klug, 1818: 287; *Dolerus laticinctus* Serville, 1823: 53; *Dolerus laticinctus* Lepeletier, 1823: 116; *Emphytus bucculentus* Tischbein, 1846: 79; *Emphytus fulvocinctus* Rudow, 1872: 217–218; *Emphytus balteatus* var. *nigripes* Konow, 1897c: 375; *Emphytus balteatus* var. *nigrolinear* Zirngiebl, 1937a: 646; *Emphytus balteatus* var. *albimacula* Zirngiebl, 1937a: 646.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan, Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa* (Liston, 1995).

53- *Allantus (Emphytus) melanarius* (Klug, 1818)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Emphytus) melanaria* Klug, 1818: 282; *Emphytus tricoloripes* Costa, 1859a: 35–36.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Mazandaran province (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: larvae feed on *Cornus sanguinea* Linnaeus (Cornaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

54- *Allantus (Allantus) viennensis* (Schrank, 1781)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo viennensis* Schrank, 1781: 331–332; *Emphytus viennensis* var. *nigricoxis* De-Stefani, 1883: 11; *Emphytus viennensis* var. *medinae* Konow, 1894b: 92; *Allantus viennensis* var. *uberior* Enslin, 1914c: 222; *Emphytus viennensis* var. *atricornis* Pic, 1948a: 11.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Abai, 2009); Alborz, Qazvin, Tehran (Khayrandish et al., in press); Gilan and Mazandaran (Behdad, 1988; Moddars Awal, 1997; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011); introduced to North America (Smith, 2003).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa* spp. and *Rubus* spp. (Berland, 1947; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Moddars Awal, 1997; Lacourt, 1999).

This species lives on several species of *Rosa* but *Rubus* is not confirmed as host (Taeger et al., 1998).

55- *Allantus (Allantus) zonarius* (Mocsáry, 1880)

Synonym: *Emphytus zonarius* Mocsáry, 1880: 268.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Mocsáry, 1880).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Mocsáry, 1880).

Host plants: Unknown.

56- *Ametastegia (Ametastegia) alabastris* (Konow, 1898)

Synonym: *Taxonus alabastris* Konow, 1898c: 238.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., 2012, 2015)

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia and Azerbaijan (Taeger & Blank, 2011), Iran (Khayrandish et al., 2012, 2015).

Host plants: Unknown.

57- *Ametastegia (Ametastegia) glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo violacea* Christ, 1791: 449; *Tenthredo glabrata* Fallén, 1808: 108; *Tenthredo (Allantus) agilis* Klug, 1817b: 208–209; *Tenthredo rufipes* Lepeletier, 1823: 81; *Tenthredo rufipes* Serville, 1823: 25; *Tenthredo (Taxonus) nigrisoma* Norton, 1862: 119; *Ametastegia fulvipes* Costa, 1882: 198; *Strongylogaster abnormis* Provancher, 1885: 10; *Strongylogastroidea potulenta* MacGillivray, 1923: 31.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Zirngiebl, 1956).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Neotropic, Australasian (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Chile, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rumex crispus* Linnaeus, *Rumex* sp., *Polygonum* sp. (Polygonaceae) in North America (Smith, 1979); *Rumex acetosella* Linnaeus *Rumex crispus*, *Rumex longifolius* De Candolle (Polygonaceae); ?*Bidens* (Asteraceae); *Chenopodium* (Chenopodiaceae); ?*Lythrum salicaria* Linnaeus (Lythraceae); *Plantago* (Plantaginaceae); *Rheum rhabarbarum* Linnaeus (Polygonaceae); *Solanum dulcamara* Linnaeus (Solanaceae); *Epilobium* (Onagraceae); *Fagopyrum* (Polygonaceae); *Solanum tuberosum* Linnaeus (Solanaceae); *Vicia* (Fabaceae); *Polygonum aviculare* Linnaeus (Polygonaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

58- *Ametastegia (Protemphytus) pallipes* (Spinola, 1808)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo pallipes* Spinola, 1808: 19; *Tenthredo (Emphytus) grossulariae* Klug, 1818: 283; *Dolerus (Emphytus) leucopodus* Lepeletier, 1823: 119; *Dolerus leucopodus* Serville, 1823: 56; *Tenthredo lapponica* Zetterstedt, 1838: 350; *Emphytus pallipes* Provancher, 1878: 66–67; *Emphytus canadensis* W.F. Kirby, 1882: 204; *Emphytus pallidipes* Dalla Torre, 1894: 119; *Empria cavata* MacGillivray, 1911: 305; *Empria cetaria* MacGillivray, 1921b: 33–34; *Emphytus hyacinthus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 16; *Emphytus hospitus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 15–16; *Emphytus halesus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 13; *Emphytus heroicus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 14–15; *Emphytus hiatus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 15.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999), Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., 2012, 2015).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); widely distributed in the European part of the West Palaearctic eastwards to Iran and has reported from Canada and U.S.A in Nearctic (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Viola canina* Linnaeus, *V. odorata* Linnaeus, *V. tricolor* Linnaeus (Violaceae) and *Vicia* (Fabaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

59- *Ametastegia (Protemphytus) persica* Khayrandish, Talebi & Blank, 2015

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., 2015).

General distribution: Iran (Khayrandish et al., 2015).

Host plants: Unknown.

60- *Ametastegia (Protemphytus) tenera* (Fallén, 1808)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo tenera* Fallén, 1808: 109; *Tenthredo (Emphytus) patellata* Klug, 1818: 283–284; *Dolerus (Emphytus) luctuosus* Lepeletier, 1823: 119; *Dolerus (Emphytus) nigrinus* Lepeletier, 1823: 120; *Dolerus*

nigrinus Serville, 1823: 57; *Dolerus luctuosus* Serville, 1823: 57; *Tenthredo trunculi* Vallot, 1845: 51; *Simplemphytus pacificus* MacGillivray, 1914: 363–364; *Emphytina vanduzeei* Rohwer, 1915: 205–206; *Emphytus haustus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 14; *Emphytus haliartus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 14; *Empria columna* MacGillivray, 1923a: 54.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Khayrandish et al., 2012, 2015).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); widely distributed in the European part of the West Palaearctic eastwards to Iran and has reported from Canada and U.S.A in Nearctic (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: *Rumex* and *Cirsium* (Asteraceae) are the main host plants for *Ametastegia tenera* but the larvae burrow into the various plant stems to pupate. Therefore some of host plants may be due to erroneous information (Taeger et al., 1998).

61- *Athalia ancilla meridiana* Benson, 1954

Synonym: *Athalia glabricollis meridiana* Benson, 1954: 279.

Distribution in Iran: Southwest of Iran (Benson, 1954, 1962, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Israel, Turkey and Uzbekistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Diplotaxis* spp., *Raphanus raphanistrum* Linnaeus, *Sisymbrium* spp. and *Sinapis* spp. (Brassicaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

62- *Athalia armeniaca* Zombori, 1978

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Gilan, Mazandaran and Tehran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

63- *Athalia circularis melanoptera* Benson, 1962

Distribution in Iran: Northeast of Iran (Lacourt, 1999; Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); China, Iran, Japan, Korea and Mongolia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

64- *Athalia cordata* Serville, 1823

Synonyms: *Athalia suessionensis* Lepelletier, 1823: 22–23; *Athalia cordata* Lepelletier, 1823: 22; *Athalia suessionensis* Serville, 1823: 80–81; *Athalia blanchardi* Brullé, 1846: 663 pl. 46; *Athalia rosae* var. *obscura* Konow, 1884: 323; *Athalia lineolata* var. *analisis* Enslin, 1913: 193.

Distribution in Iran: East Azerbaijan (Chevin, 1985); Gilan and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Ajuga reptans* Linnaeus (Lamiaceae), *Antirrhinum* Linnaeus and *Plantago* Linnaeus (Plantaginaceae) (Liston 1995); Labiatae and Plantaginaceae (Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993); *Ajuga* spp., *Antirrhinum* spp., *Misopates orontium* (Linnaeus) (Plantaginaceae), *Teucrium scorodonia* Linnaeus (Lamiaceae), *Plantago* spp. (Lacourt, 1999). *Misopates orontium*, *Antirrhinum majus* Linnaeus, *Ajuga reptans*, *Plantago* are confirmed as hosts for *Athalia cordata* and other species are not clear (Taeger et al., 1998).

65- *Athalia cornubiae* Benson, 1931

Distribution in Iran: Southwest of Iran (Benson, 1962, 1968; Dadurian, 1962).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary,

Iran, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, USA and Uzbekistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Sedum album* Linnaeus and *S. hispanicum* Linnaeus (Crassulaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998, Lacourt, 1999).

66- *Athalia liberta* (Klug, 1815)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *rosae* var. *liberta* Klug, 1815: 129; *Athalia rosae* var. *immaculata* Konow, 1884: 323.

Distribution in Iran: Southwest of Iran (Benson, 1962, 1968; Dadurian, 1962); Golestan (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999); Alborz, Qazvin, Gilan and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Sisymbrium* spp., *Alliaria petiolata* (M.Bieberstein) and *Cardamine* spp. (Brassicaceae) (Berland, 1947; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Lacourt, 1999). *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Linnaeus), *Alliaria petiolata*, *Cardamine hirsuta* Linnaeus, *Sisymbrium officinale* (Linnaeus) are as hosts for *A. liberta* but other species of *Cardamine* and *Sisymbrium* are not confirmed (Taeger et al., 1998).

67- *Athalia paveli* Mocsáry, 1879

Distribution in Iran: Fars province (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: Iran and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

68- *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonym: *Tenthredo rosae* Linnaeus, 1758: 557.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press); East Azerbaijan (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Modarres Awal, 1997; Benson, 1968) and Golestan (Mallach, 1931; Chevin, 1985) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Armoracia rusticana* Gaertner, Meyer & Scherbius, *Barbarea* W. T. Aiton, *Brassica juncea* (Linnaeus), *Brassica napus* Linnaeus, *Brassica nigra* Linnaeus, *Brassica rapa* Linnaeus, *Rorippa amphibian* (Linnaeus), *Sinapis alba* Linnaeus, *Sisymbrium officinale*, *Brassica oleracea* Linnaeus, *Raphanus raphanistrum* Linnaeus, *Sinapis arvensis* Linnaeus (Brassicaceae) and *Tropaeolum majus* Linnaeus (Tropaeolaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

69- *Empria pravei* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1925

Additional records from Iran: Mazandaran province (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Iran and Russia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

Remarks: Khayrandish et al. (in press) reported a species as *E. nr pravei* from Gilan and Mazandaran provinces that might represent a new species close to *E. pravei*.

70- *Eriocampa peineae* Zirngiebl, 1956

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Gilan (Zirngiebl, 1956; Blank, 1996; Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et

al., in press) and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran and Russia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

71- *Monosoma pulveratum* (Retzius, 1783)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo pulverata* Retzius, 1783: 72; *Tenthredo limbata* Gmelin, 1790: 2667; *Tenthredo pulverulenta* Christ, 1791: 451–452; *Tenthredo (Allantus) obesa* Klug, 1817b: 210–211; *Tenthredo (Allantus) obtusa* Klug, 1817b: 211–212; *Selandria pulchella* Stephens, 1835: 54; *Tenthredo leucozonias* Hartig, 1837: 290; *Tenthredo segmentata* Zetterstedt, 1838: 353; *Harpiphorus taeniatus* Costa, 1869: 14; *Empria pulverata* var. *obtusalis* Enslin, 1914c: 210–211.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Zirngiebl, 1956; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Alnus incana* (Linnaeus), *A. glutinosa* (Linnaeus) and *Salix* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998); *A. glutinosa*, *A. incana*, *A. orientalis* Decaisne (Betulaceae) (Lacourt, 1999).

Subfamily Blennocampinae

72- *Ardis pallipes* (Serville, 1823)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) bipunctata* Klug, 1817b: 215; *Dolerus pallipes* Serville, 1823: 57; *Dolerus (Emphytus) pallipes* Lepeletier, 1823: 119–120; *Tenthredo brunniventris* Hartig, 1837: 274; *Monophadnus dissimilis* Costa, 1859a: 54–55; *Selandria (Monophadnus) irrogata* Cresson, 1880: 13; *Emphytus dubius* W.F. Kirby, 1882:

202; *Aphanisus odoratus* MacGillivray, 1908: 296; *Aphanisus parallelus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 7–8.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009); Alborz, Tehran (Esmaili et al., 1991) and Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Canada, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa pimpinellifolia*, *R. alpina* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998).

73- *Cladardis elongatula* (Klug, 1817)

Synonym: *Tenthredo (Allantus) elongatula* Klug, 1817b: 214.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Behdad, 1988; Esmaili et al., 1991; Modarres Awal, 1997; Aabi, 2009).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010) Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa* (Taeger et al. 1998, Lacourt, 1999).

74- *Eutomostethus luteiventris* (Klug, 1816)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) luteiventris* Klug, 1816: 56–57; *Tenthredo fuscipennis* Lepeletier, 1823: 107; *Tenthredo fuscipennis* Serville, 1823: 49–50; *Phyllotoma fuscipennis* Fallén, 1829: 29–30.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Juncus effusus* Linnaeus (Juncaceae) (Benson, 1952; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

75- *Halidamia affinis* (Fallén, 1807)

Synonyms: *Hylotoma affinis* Fallén, 1807: 207; *Tenthredo (Allantus) hyaline* Klug, 1816: 58; *Blennocampa assimilis* Thomson, 1870: 282; *Blennocampa formosella* Costa, 1882: 198; *Blennocampa affinis* var. *pleuritica* Enslin, 1914c: 294.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Morocco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Galium aparinae* Linnaeus and *G. mollugo* Linnaeus (Rubiaceae) (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1952; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

76- *Monophadnoides rubi* (Harris, 1845)

Synonyms: *Selandria (Hoplocampa) rubi* T.W. Harris, 1845: 13; *Selandria (Monophadnus) nigella* Cresson, 1880: 12; *Monophadnus hudsonicus* W.F. Kirby, 1882: 176; *Monophadnus atricornus* MacGillivray, 1893: 239; *Monophadnus atricornis* Konow, 1905a: 86; *Blennocampa gillettei* Weldon,

1907: 304; *Monophadnoides consobrinus* MacGillivray, 1908: 294; *Monophadnoides costalis* MacGillivray, 1908: 295; *Monophadnoides coracinus* MacGillivray, 1908: 295; *Monophadnoides collaris* MacGillivray, 1908: 295; *Monophadnoides conspicuus* MacGillivray, 1908: 293; *Monophadnoides conspersus* MacGillivray, 1908: 294-295; *Monophadnoides craessus* MacGillivray, 1908: 294; *Monophadnoides concessus* MacGillivray, 1908: 294; *Aphanisus nigritus* MacGillivray, 1908: 296; *Aphanisus lenis* Rohwer, 1909: 399; *Monophadnoides costatus* MacGillivray, 1916: 152-153; *Monophadnoides kincaidi* MacGillivray, 1923e: 26; *Monophadnoides shawi* MacGillivray, 1923e: 26; *Monophadnoides consonus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 25; *Monophadnoides constitutus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 25; *Monophadnoides corytus* MacGillivray, 1923d: 79; *Monophadnoides curiosus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 25-26; *Paracharactus obversus* MacGillivray, 1923e: 28.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Filipendula ulmaria* (Linnaeus), *Geum urbanum* Linnaeus and *Rubus* (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

77- *Monophadnoides scythia* (Konow, 1898)

Synonym: *Monophadnus scythia* Konow, 1898c: 236-237.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999; Pesarini, 2004).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

78- *Pareophora pumilio* Konow, 1898

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Mazandaran (Benson, 1968) and Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan and Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae of *Pareophora* species feed on *Prunus* (Rosaceae) (Benson, 1952) but for *Pareophora pumilio* is unknown.

79- *Tomostethus claripennis* Enslin, 1914

Synonym: *Tomostethus nigritus* var. *claripennis* Enslin, 1914b: 167.

Distribution in Iran: Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad (Abai and Moghadam, 1993; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009) and Lorestan (Abai, 2009) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Morocco, Spain and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Fraxinus excelsior* Linnaeus (Oleaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

Subfamily Heterarthrinae

80- *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo cerasi* Linnaeus, 1758: 557; *Tenthredo flavipes* Schrank, 1781: 340; *Tenthredo limacina* Retzius, 1783: 73; *Tenthredo (Allantus) adumbrata* Klug, 1816: 64; *Monostegia antipoda* W.F. Kirby, 1881: 50; *Caliroa laudata* MacGillivray, 1909: 355-356; *Caliroa lacinata* MacGillivray, 1909: 356-357.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Abai, 2009; Behdad, 1984; Behdad, 1988; Farahbakhsh, 1961; Modarres Awal, 1997); Western provinces (Abai, 2009; Behdad, 1984; Modarres Awal, 1997); Azerbaijan (Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009); Gilan, Mazandaran (Esmaili, 1983; Esmaili et al., 1991); Kermanshah (Behdad, 1984; Modarres Awal, 1997) and Kordistan (Farahbakhsh, 1961) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental, Afrotropics, Australian,

Neotropic (Taeger et al., 2010); Algeria, Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Colombia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Luxembourg, Malta, Moldova, Morocco, Netherlands, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, Uruguay, USA, Uzbekistan and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are polyphagous feeding on *Cotoneaster* Medikus, *Malus* Miller, *Betula* and *Mespilus germanica* Linnaeus (Rosaceae), *Quercus*, *Rosa*, *Rubus*, *Salix*, *Amelanchier lamarckii* Scheroeder, *Crataegus monogyna* Jacquin (Rosaceae), *Cydonia oblonga* Miller (Rosaceae), *Prunus cerasus* Linnaeus, *Prunus domestica* Linnaeus, *Prunus padus* Linnaeus, *Prunus spinosa* Linnaeus, *Pyrus communis* Linnaeus, *Rosa canina*, *Sorbus aucuparia* Linnaeus, *Crataegus* Tournefort, *Prunus persica* (Linnaeus) (Rosaceae), *Crataegus sanguinea* Pallas, *Prunus serrulata* Lindley (Taeger et al., 1998).

Remarks: Khayrandish et al. (in press) reported a species from Gilan and Mazandaran provinces that was very similar to *C. cerasi*, but exact identification was not possible.

81- *Caliroa* nr *varipes* (Klug, 1816)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) varipes* Klug, 1816: 69; *Eriocampa crassicornis* Tischbein, 1846: 113; *Eriocampoides variipes* Dalla Torre, 1894: 196.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands,

Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Quercus robur* Linnaeus (Fagaceae) and maybe some species of *Quercus* (Taeger et al., 1998).

82- *Fenusa (Kaliofenusa) ulmi* Sundevall, 1847

Synonyms: *Fenusa intermedia* Thomson, 1871: 186; *Messa alsia* MacGillivray, 1923e: 22-23.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Abai, 2009) and Tehran province (Abai, 1994; Abai, 2009).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Iran, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Ulmus glabra* Hudson, *U. minor* Miller, *U. foliacea* Gilibert, ?*U. americana* Linnaeus, *U. elliptica* Kokh and *U. rubra* Muhlenberg (Ulmaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

83- *Fenusella hortulana* (Klug, 1818)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Emphytus) hortulana* Klug, 1818: 276; *Phoenusa doderleini* De-Stefani, 1883: 12-13; *Fenusella sonderupi* Hering, 1935: XII.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kyrgyzstan, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Populus nigra* Linnaeus, *Acer campestre* Linnaeus, *A. platanoides* Linnaeus

(Berland, 1947); *Populus nigra* (Benson, 1952; Liston, 1995); *Populus* spp. (Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Lacourt, 1999). *Populus alba* Linnaeus, *Populus nigra*, *Populus balsamifera* Linnaeus, *Populus x canadensis* Moench, *Populus nigra* var. *italica* Du Rui are confirmed as hosts for *F. hortulana* and other species of *populous* or *Acer* are not clear (Taeger et al., 1998).

84- *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818)

Synonym: *Tenthredo (Emphytus) microcephala* Klug, 1818: 274-275.

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feed on *Salix pentandra* Linnaeus, *S. caprea* Linnaeus, *S. phylicifolia* Linnaeus, *S. alba* Linnaeus, *S. viminalis* Linnaeus, *S. aurita* Linnaeus, *S. myrsinifolia* Salisbury, *S. repens* Linnaeus, *S. cinerea* Linnaeus, *S. fragilis* Linnaeus, *S. purpurea* Linnaeus, *S. triandra* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

85- *Metallus beckeri* (Konow, 1904)

Synonym: *Entodecta beckeri* Konow, 1904a: 4-5.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Georgia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus idaeus* (Linnaeus), *R. crataegifolius* Bertoloni (Lacourt, 1999).

86- *Metallus pumilus* (Klug, 1816)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) pumila* Klug, 1816: 72; *Emphytus pumilio* Hartig, 1837: 259; *Fenusa rubi* Boie, 1848: 340.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus caesius* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998).

87- *Scolioneura hyrcana* Benson, 1968

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999) and Mazandaran province (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

Subfamily Nematinae

88- *Amauronematus* (*Amauronematus*) *tunicatus* (Zaddach, 1883)

Synonyms: *Nematus tunicatus* Zaddach in Brischke, 1883b: 166-167; *Nematus laevis* Brischke, 1883b: 174-175.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia and Sweden (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Salix aurita* Linnaeus, *S. atrocinnerea* Brotero, *S. caprea*, *S. acuminata* Miller, *S. cinerea* (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1958; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Lacourt, 1999).

89- *Cladius* (*Priophorus*) *brullei* (Dahlbom, 1835)

Synonyms: *Cladius immunis* Stephens, 1835: 24; *Nematus melanostigma* Stephens, 1835: 35-36; *Nematus* (*Priophorus*) *geniculatus*

Dahlbom, 1835a: 7; *Nematus* (*Priophorus*) *brullei* Dahlbom, 1835a: 7; *Cladius tener* Zaddach, 1859: 11; *Cladius tristis* Zaddach, 1859: 11-12; *Cladius parvus* Zaddach in Brischke, 1883: 225; *Priophorus rubivorus* Rohwer in Rohwer & Middleton, 1922: 28-29; *Priophorus montanus* Rohwer in Rohwer & Middleton, 1922: 31; *Priophorus rubi* Rohwer in Rohwer & Middleton, 1922: 32; *Priophorus foveivaginatatus* Malaise, 1931: 148-149.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999); Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental, Australasian, Neotropic (Taeger et al., 2010); Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Chile, China, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, India, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus* (Berland, 1947; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Lacourt, 1999); *Rubus* spp., *Sorbus aucuparia* Linnaeus (Rosaceae) (Benson, 1958); *Rubus arcticus* (Linnaeus), *R. idaeus*, *R. saxatilis* (Linnaeus), *R. fruticosus* (Linnaeus) are confirmed as hosts for *C. brullei* (Taeger et al., 1998).

90- *Cladius* (*Cladius*) *pectinicornis* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo pectinicornis* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 374; *Tenthredo alces* Thunberg, 1789: unpage; *Tenthredo difformis* Panzer, 1799: 62: 10; *Cladius geoffroyi* Lapeletier, 1823: 58; *Cladius geoffroyi* Serville, 1823: 77; *Cladius morio* Lapeletier, 1823: 58-59; *Cladius morio* Serville, 1823: 78; *Tenthredo* (*Cladius*) *isomera* T.W. Harris, 1835: 583; *Nematus crassicornis* Stephens,

1835: 28; *Cladius isomera* Norton, 1861: 223; *Cladius ramicornis* André, 1880: 80; *Cladius gracilicornis* Konow, 1884: 314–316; *Cladius crassicornis* Konow, 1884: 14; *Cladius comari* Stein, 1886: 35–37; *Cladius hyalinopterus* Konow, 1886a: 74–75; *Cladius palmicornis* Konow, 1892: 212; *Cladius major* Cobelli, 1892: 70; *Cladius ordubadensis* Konow, 1892: 211–212; *Cladius orientalis* Cameron, 1902: 448; *Cladius tibialatus* Konow, 1906: 256.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968); Alborz, Qazvin, Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, India, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Moldova, Morocco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rosa*, *Fragaria*, *Potentilla palustris*, *Filipendula ulmaria* (Linnaeus), *Sanguisorba minor* Scopoli, *Alchemilla vulgaris* Linnaeus (Rosaceae), *Lamiastrum galeobdolon* (Linnaeus) (Lamiaceae) (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1958; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Lacourt, 1999); ?*Filipendula ulmaria*, ?*Galeobdolon luteum* (Linnaeus) (Rosaceae), ?*Sanguisorba minor*, ?*Alchemilla vulgaris*, ?*Fragaria*, ?*Potentilla palustris* Linnaeus (Rosaceae) (*Comarum palustre*), *Rosa hybrida* Linnaeus, *Rosa luciae* Franchet & Rochebrune, *Rosa multiflora* Thunberg, *Rosa wichuraiana* Crepin, *Rosa canina*, *Rosa acicularis* Lindley (Taeger et al., 1998); *Rosa* (Liston & Späth, 2005).

91- *Cladius (Priophorus) rufipes* Serville, 1823

Synonyms: *Cladius rufipes* Serville, 1823: 78; *Cladius rufipes* Lepeletier, 1823: 58; *Cladius*

(*Trichiocampus*) *uncinnata* Hartig, 1837: 176–177; *Cladius discrepans* Costa, 1859a: 11–12; *Trichiocampus garbigliettii* Costa, 1864: 103; *Priophorus phaeopterus* Costa, 1894: 45.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan (Khosravi et al., 2014) and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belarus, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Ulmus* (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1968; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999); *Ulmus densa* (Khosravi et al., 2014).

92- *Craesus medunai* Beneš & Abai, 1991

Synonym: *Croesus medunai* Beneš & Abai, 1991: 253–263.

Distribution in Iran: Tehran province (Beneš & Abai, 1991; Abai, 2009).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Beneš & Abai, 1991).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Betula pendula* Roth (Beneš & Abai, 1991).

93- *Craesus persicus* Beneš, 1981

Synonym: *Croesus persicus* Beneš, 1981: 177–182.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Northern provinces (Abai, 2009); Alborz, Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Beneš, 1981; Beneš & Abai, 1991; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Beneš, 1981; Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Alnus subcordata* C.A. von Meyer (Beneš, 1981).

94- *Euura (Euura) sp. (atra group)*

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Sweden, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Salix alba* and *S. fragilis* (Taeger et al., 1998).

95- *Hoplocampa brevis* (Klug, 1816)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *brevis* Klug, 1816: 53–54; *Tenthredo fallax* Lepeletier, 1823: 108; *Tenthredo fallax* Serville, 1823: 50; *Tenthredo pyri* Vallot, 1848: 203.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Esmaili, 1983; Esmaili et al., 1991); Alborz (Davoudi, 1987; Radjabi, 2002); Isfahan (Behdad, 1984; Modarres Awal, 1997); Qazvin (Radjabi, 2002) and Tehran (Behdad, 1984; Davoudi, 1987; Modarres Awal, 1997) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Canada, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Pyrus communis* (Taeger et al., 1998).

96- *Hoplocampa crataegi* (Klug, 1816)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *crataegi* Klug, 1816: 54; *Tenthredo pallida* Lepeletier, 1823: 105; *Tenthredo luteola* Lepeletier, 1823: 108; *Tenthredo pallida* Serville, 1823: 47; *Tenthredo luteola* Serville, 1823: 50–51; *Tenthredo verticata* Lepeletier, 1823: 108; *Tenthredo verticata* Serville, 1823: 50.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium,

Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Crataegus* (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1968; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999); swept from *Crataegus monogyna* Jacquin (Liston & Späth, 2005).

97- *Hoplocampa flava* (Linnaeus, 1760)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo flava* Linnaeus, 1760: 395; *Tenthredo ruficapilla* Gmelin, 1790: 2668; *Tenthredo glaucopsis* Rossi, 1790: vol. 2, 31–32; *Allantus ferrugineus* Panzer, 1803: 90: 9; *Hylotoma ferruginea* Fabricius, 1804: 26; *Hylotoma simplex* Fallén, 1807: 207–208; *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *brunnea* Klug, 1816: 53; *Hoplocampa flava* var. *dimidiata* Costa, 1894: 149; *Tomostethus testaceus* Niezabitowski, 1899: 12.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Esmaili, 1983; Esmaili et al., 1991; Davoudi, 1993; Modarres Awal, 1997); Alborz and Qazvin provinces and so most other plum planting areas (Radjabi, 2002).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belarus, Belgium, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Latvia, Lebanon, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Prunus domestica* Linnaeus, *P. avium* Linnaeus, *P. cerasus* Linnaeus, *P. mahaleb* (Linnaeus) and *P. spinosa* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998).

98- *Hoplocampa minuta* (Christ, 1791)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo minuta* Christ, 1791: 438; *Tenthredo hylotomoides* Lepeletier, 1823: 107; *Tenthredo hylotomoides* Serville, 1823: 49; *Tenthredo parvula* Lepeletier, 1823: 107;

Tenthredo paroula Serville, 1823: 49;
Tenthredo turcarum Vallot, 1848: 206;
Hoplocampa fabricii W.F. Kirby, 1882: 167;
Hoplocampa minuta forma *dudai* Gregor in
 Gregor & Bařa, 1942: 288.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Esmaili, 1983; Esmaili et al., 1991); Hamadan, Isfahan, Tehran (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1984; Modarres Awal, 1997); Qazvin, Markazi (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Behdad, 1984); Mazandaran and Zanzan (Modarres Awal, 1997) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Prunus armeniaca* (Linnaeus), *P. avium*, *P. domestica* and *P. spinosa* (Taeger et al., 1998).

99- *Hoplocampa pectoralis* Thomson, 1871

Synonyms: *Hoplocampa gallicola* Cameron, 1877: 156-157; *Hoplocampa oertzeni* Konow, 1888b: 188,190.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999) and Mazandaran province (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Crataegus* (Taeger et al., 1998).

100- *Hoplocampa testudinea* (Klug, 1816)

Synonym: *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *testudinea* Klug, 1816: 60.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Behdad, 1984; Modarres Awal, 1997).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia,

Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, Sweden, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Pyrus malus* Linnaeus and *P. communis* (Taeger et al., 1998).

101- *Nematus (Paranematus) sp.*

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

Host plants: Unknown.

102- *Nematus (Pteronidea) fagi* Zaddach, 1876

Synonym: *Nematus fagi kanazawaensis* Togashi, 1972: 63.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Fagus sylvatica* Linnaeus (Fagaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

103- *Nematus (Pteronidea) incompletus* Förster, 1854

Synonyms: *Nematus incompletus* Förster, 1854a: 297-298; *Nematus smaragdinus* Stein, 1881: 60-62; *Nematus pulchellus* Cameron, 1882b: 537-538; *Nematus chlorogaster* Zaddach in Brischke, 1884: 149-150; *Pteronidea segmentaria* var. *signata* Enslin, 1916: 426; *Pteronidea segmentaria* var. *tessinensis* Enslin, 1916: 426.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldova,

Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Salix* and *Populus tremula* Linnaeus (Salicaceae) (Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998).

104- *Nematus (Nematus) lucidus* (Panzer, 1801)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo lucida* Panzer, 1801: 82: 10; *Nematus cinctus* Lepeletier, 1823: 66; *Nematus cinctus* Serville, 1823: 68–69; *Nematus (Nematus) devillareti* Dahlbom, 1835b: 10; *Holcoeneme lucidus* var. *rufa* Zirngiebl, 1937b: 347.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Crataegus* and *Prunus spinosa* (Taeger et al., 1998).

105- *Nematus (Pteronidea) oligospilus* Förster, 1854

Synonyms: *Nematus mendicus* Walsh, 1866: 261–262; *Nematus trivittatus* Norton, 1867a: 218; *Nematus microcercus* Thomson, 1871: 152; *Nematus dorsivittatus* Cresson, 1880: 10; *Nematus salicivorus* Cameron, 1882a: 194–195; *Pteronus koebelei* Marlatt, 1896: 44–46 (key), 71; *Pteronidea vanduzeei* Rohwer, 1913: 280–281; *Pteronidea elelea* MacGillivray, 1923b: 162; *Nematus desantisi* D.R. Smith, 1983: 260–262.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Qazvin provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Neotropic, Afrotropic, Australasian (Taeger et al., 2010); Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Chile,

Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lesotho, Netherlands, New Zealand, Pakistan, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagous feeding on *Salix fragilis*, *S. pentandra* Linnaeus, *S. alba*, *S. caprea* and *S. hastata* Linnaeus (Benson, 1958; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

106- *Nematus (Pteronidea) scotonotus* Förster, 1854

Synonyms: *Pteronidea fuscodorsata* Lindqvist, 1949: 73–74; *Nematus polygona* Benson, 1961: 228–229.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Finland, France and Germany (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Polygonum bistorta* (Linnaeus) (Polygonaceae) (Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

107- *Pontania (Pontania) proxima* (Serville, 1823)

Synonyms: *Nematus proximus* Serville, 1823: 69; *Nematus proximus* Lepeletier, 1823: 67–68; *Nematus gallicola* Stephens, 1835: 36; *Nematus vallisnerii* Hartig, 1837: 205–207; *Nematus redii* Contarini, 1852: 129–130; *Pontania gallicola* Costa, 1852: 1–17; *Nematus albicarpus* Costa, 1859a: 22–23; *Messa hyalina* Norton, 1864: 8; *Nematus festivus* Zaddach in Brischke, 1884: 146–147; *Euura flavipes* Cameron, 1885: 211–212; *Pontania daedala* MacGillivray, 1921a: 33–34.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic, Australasian (Taeger et al., 2010); Australia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium,

Bulgaria, Canada, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Moldova, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and USA (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Salix alba* and *S. fragilis* (Taeger et al., 1998), *S. alba* (Liston & Späth, 2005).

108- *Pontania (Eupontania) vesicator (Bremi-Wolf, 1849)*

Synonyms: *Nematus vesicator* Bremi-Wolf, 1849: 93–94; *Nematus hellicinus* Brischke, 1850: 409–410; *Nematus leptocerus* Förster, 1854a: 289–291; *Nematus lugdunensis* Snellen van Vollenhoven, 1871: 243–248; *Nematus vesicator* var. *minor* Brischke, 1883b: 173; *Pontania vesicator* ab. *borealis* Saarinen, 1945: 194–195.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Behdad, 1988; Modarres Awal, 1997; Abai, 2009).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Salix purpurea* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

109- *Pristiphora (Pristiphora) aphantoneura (Förster, 1854)*

Synonyms: *Nematus aphantoneurus* Förster, 1854a: 323–325; *Cryptocampus distinctus* Costa, 1882: 198; *Pristiphora pygmaea* Lindqvist, 1964: 130.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, China, Estonia, Finland,

Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Salix aurita* Linnaeus (Berland, 1947; Taeger et al., 1998).

110- *Pristiphora (Gymnonychus) biscalis (Förster, 1854)*

Synonyms: *Nematus biscalis* Förster, 1854a: 326–327; *Nematus conspersus* Zaddach in Brischke, 1883b: 186; *Nematus pruni* Brischke, 1883a: pl. I, 2; *Nematus lateralis* Brischke, 1885: 246; *Nematus postumus* Dalla Torre, 1894: 251.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Prunus spinosa*, *Rosa canina* and *Dasiphora fruticosa* (Linnaeus) (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

111- *Pristiphora (Pristiphora) conjugata (Dahlbom, 1835)*

Synonyms: *Nematus conjugatus* Dahlbom, 1835b: 21–22, 40; *Nematus gonymelas* Stephens, 1835: 34; *Nematus (Nematus) conjugatus* Dahlbom, 1835a: 8; *Nematus discipennis* Herrich-Schäffer, 1840: 176; *Nematus discoidalis* Thomson, 1888: 1209–1210; *Pristiphora conjugata* var. *ulbrichti* Enslin, 1916: 534.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999); Alborz (Chevin, 1985) and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Netherlands,

Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Populus tremula*, *P. italica*, *Salix fragilis*, *S. alba vitellina* (*S. vitellina*) and *S. caprea* (Taeger et al., 1998).

112- *Pristiphora* (*Pristiphora*) *pallidiventr* (Fallen, 1808)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo pallidiventr* Fallén, 1808: 120–121; *Nematus* (*Nematus*) *luridus* Dahlbom, 1835a: 7; *Nematus ephippiger* Hartig, 1840: 24; *Nematus flavicomus* Tischbein, 1846: 77; *Nematus caudalis* Eversmann, 1847: 16; *Nematus nigricans* Eversmann, 1847: 16; *Nematus breviusculus* Eversmann, 1847: 17; *Nematus gemellus* Förster, 1854b: 425–427; *Nematus marshalli* Cameron, 1875: 9; *Nematus cirrhostomus* Zaddach in Brischke, 1883b: 195; *Pristiphora pallidiventr* var. *denudata* Konow, 1902a: 165, 179; *Pristiphora zella* Rohwer, 1909: 20; *Pristiphora pallicoxa* Rohwer, 1910b: 200; *Pristiphora xanthotrachela* Rohwer, 1913: 281; *Pristiphora pallidiventr* var. *haemorrhoidalis* Enslin, 1916: 526; *Pristiphora pallidiventr* var. *stigmatica* Enslin, 1916: 526; *Pristiphora ostiaria* MacGillivray, 1920: 236; *Nematus* (*Pristiphora*) *pallidiventr* ab. *flaviapex* Hellén, 1948: 45; *Nematus* (*Pristiphora*) *pallidiventr* ab. *nigrofemoratus* Hellén, 1948: 45; *Pristiphora pallidiventr* *megalpina* Lacourt, 1987: 262–264.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden,

Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus idaeus*, *Filipendula*, *Geum urbanum* Linnaeus, *Potentilla* (Rosaceae) and *Ribes* (Grossulariaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

113- *Pristiphora* (*Stauronematus*) *platycerus* (Hartig, 1840)

Synonyms: *Nematus platycerus* Hartig, 1840: 27; *Nematus vallator* Snellen van Vollenhoven, 1858b: 191–194; *Nematus cebrionicornis* Costa, 1859a: 20; *Nematus callicerus* Thomson, 1863: 619–620.

Distribution in Iran: Northern provinces (Cavalcassele, 1968; Abai, 2009); Alborz, Isfahan, Tehran (Cavalcassele, 1968); Gilan, Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press); Golestan (Chevin, 1985) and Markazi (Abai, 2009) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Populus tremula*, *P. italic*, *P. sieboldii* Miquel and *Salix alopechroa* (Taeger et al., 1998).

Subfamily Selandriinae

114- *Aneugmenus coronatus* (Klug, 1818)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo* (*Emphytus*) *coronata* Klug, 1818: 276; *Selandria analis* Thomson, 1871: 239; *Selandria cereipes* Snellen van Vollenhoven, 1873: 13–15; *Selandria bimaculata* Cobelli, 1892: 71–72; *Selandria ogloblini* Dovnar-Zapolskij, 1930: 90–91.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great

Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Dryopteris filix-mas* (Linnaeus) (Dryopteridaceae), *Aspidium Swartz* (Tectariaceae), *Athyrium filix-femina* (Linnaeus) (Athyriaceae), *Pteridium aquilinum* (Linnaeus) (Dennstaedtiaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

115- *Aneugmenus padi* (Linnaeus, 1760)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo padi* Linnaeus, 1760: 390; *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *stramineipes* Klug, 1816: 75–76; *Tenthredo albipes* Lepeletier, 1823: 105; *Tenthredo albipes* Serville, 1823: 47–48; *Selandria rufitarsis* Brullé, 1832: 394; *Allantus laticinctus* Brullé, 1832: 392; *Tenthredo* (*Selandria*) *cerasorum* Dahlbom, 1835a: 11; *Selandria vollenhoveni* Gribodo, 1881: 50; *Selandria* (*Aneugmenus*) *urbis* Ross, 1930: 186–188.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Zirngiebl, 1956; Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Pteridium aquilinum* and *Asplenium* Linnaeus (Aspleniaceae) (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1952; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

116- *Dolerus (Dolerus) hispanicus* Mocsáry, 1881

Synonyms: *Dolerus africanus* Forsius, 1918b: 2–3; *Dolerus persicus* Haris, 1996: 190–191.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1977) and Kordistan province (Haris, 1996).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran and Spain (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Northwest of Africa, Spain, Turkey, Transcaucasia and Iran (Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Larvae feed on ?*Equisetum ramosissimum* Desfontaines (Lacourt, 1999).

117- *Dolerus hyrcanus* Benson, 1968

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999); Gilan, Markazi (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999; Taeger & Blank, 2011); Caucasus (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

Host plants: Unknown.

118- *Dolerus (Poodolerus) kokujewi* Konow, 1902

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999) and Alborz province (Chevin, 1985).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Israel, Russia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

119- *Dolerus (Dolerus) nigriceps* Konow, 1891

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Russia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

Remark: Lacourt (1999) is not a primary source so this record is not confirmed.

120- *Dolerus (Poodolerus) puncticollis* Thomson, 1871

Synonym: *Dolerus croaticus* Konow, 1890a: 9.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999) and Mazandaran province (Chevin, 1985);

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech

Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Dactylis glomerata* Linnaeus (Poaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

121- *Dolerus (Dicrodolerus) vestigialis* (Klug, 1818)

Synonym: *Tenthredo (Dolerus) vestigialis* Klug, 1818: 305–306.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999) and Mazandaran province (Chevin, 1985, Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Equisetum palustre* Linnaeus, *E. sylvaticum* Linnaeus, *E. arvense* Linnaeus and *E. pratense* Ehrhart (Equisetaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

122- *Nesoselandria morio* (Fabricius, 1781)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo morio* Fabricius, 1781: 414; *Tenthredo ulmi* Schrank, 1802: 237; *Tenthredo tristis* Lepeletier, 1823: 106; *Tenthredo tristis* Serville, 1823: 48–49; *Emphytus infuscatus* Eversmann, 1847: 29; *Selandria fabricii* Konow, 1885b: 300; *Aneugmenus brunneus* Magretti, 1886: 25.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Brachythecium reflexum* Schimper (Brachytheciaceae), *Plagiothecium denticulatum* (Hedwig) (Plagiotheciaceae), *Polytrichum commune* Hedwig (Polytrichaceae), *Sanionia uncinata* (Hedwig) (Amblystegiaceae), *Ceratodon purpureus* (Hedwig) (Ditrichaceae), *Dicranum scoparium* Hedwig (Dicranaceae), *Hedwigia ciliata* Hedwig (Hedwigiaceae), *Plagiomnium cuspidatum* (Hedwig) (Mniaceae), *Pseudobryum cinclidioides* (Huebener) (Mniaceae) and so eggs of *N. morio* have observed on *Stellaria media* (Linnaeus) (Caryophyllaceae), *Veronica chamaedrys* Linnaeus (Plantaginaceae), *Veronica officinalis* Linnaeus (Plantaginaceae), *Chenopodium album* Linnaeus (Chenopodiaceae), *Fragaria vesca* Linnaeus (Rosaceae), *Myosotis arvensis* (Linnaeus) (Boraginaceae), *Polygonum aviculare* Linnaeus (Polygonaceae), *Ceratodon purpureus*, *Dicranum scoparium*, *Hedwigia ciliate*, *Plagiomnium cuspidatum* and *Pseudobryum cinclidioides* (Taeger et al., 1998).

123- *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo serva* Fabricius, 1793: 110; *Hylotoma serva* var. *mascula* Fallén, 1807: 204; *Tenthredo (Allantus) socia* Klug, 1816: 49–50; *Tenthredo lepida* Lepeletier, 1823: 104; *Tenthredo lepida* Serville, 1823: 46–47; *Selandria dorsalis* Stephens, 1835: 45–46; *Selandria excisa* Konow, 1885a: 24–25; *Selandria serva* var. *interstitialis* Konow, 1885a: 23; *Selandria serva fuscitarsis* Benson, 1954: 276; *Selandria serva* var. *punctatus* Zirngiebl, 1956: 322.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan (Zirngiebl, 1956; Blank, 1996) and Mazandaran (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Poa* Linnaeus, *Carex* Linnaeus (Cyperaceae), *Juncus* Linnaeus (Juncaceae), *Triticum*, *Alopecurus pratensis* Linnaeus (Poaceae), *Festuca pratensis* Hudson (Poaceae), *Lolium* Linnaeus (Poaceae), *Phalaris arundinacea*, *Phleum pretense* Linnaeus (Poaceae), *P. pratensis* (Taeger et al., 1998).

124- *Strongylogaster multifasciata* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo multifasciata* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 368; *Tenthredo lineata* Christ, 1791: 450; *Tenthredo (Allantus) linearis* Klug, 1817b: 217–218; *Tenthredo alternans* Lepeletier, 1823: 73; *Tenthredo alternans* Serville, 1823: 17; *Strongylogaster iridipennis* F. Smith, 1874: 377; *Strongylogaster caucasicus* Schaposchnikov, 1885: 181–182; *Strongylogaster cretensis* Konow, 1887a: 26; *Strongylogaster annularis* Matsumura, 1912: 219–220; *Strongylogaster lineata cypria* Benson, 1954: 276.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1958); Gilan (Zirngiebl, 1956; Khayrandish et al., in press); Golestan (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999); Lorestan (Mallach, 1931) and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic, Oriental (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great

Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lebanon, Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Dryopteris Adanson* (Dryopteridaceae), *Matteuccia struthiopteris* (Linnaeus) (Onocleaceae), *Aspidium*, *Polystichum* Roth (Dryopteridaceae), *Pteridium aquilinum* (Taeger et al., 1998).

Subfamily Tenthredininae

125- *Aglaostigma (Astochus) aucupariae* (Klug, 1817)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) aucupariae* Klug, 1817b: 212–213; *Tenthredo juvenilis* Lepeletier, 1823: 99; *Tenthredo juvenilis* Serville, 1823: 40–41; *Allantus collaris* Dietrich, 1868: 354; *Laurentia craverii* Costa, 1890: 14–15; *Macrophya laticarpus* Kriechbaumer, 1891: 188–189; *Aglaostigma aucupariae lacteore* Benson, 1968: 155.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Galium aparine* (Linnaeus), *G. mollugo* (Linnaeus), *G. verum* (Linnaeus) and *G. boreale* (Linnaeus) (Rubiaceae) (Berland, 1947; Benson, 1952; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

126- *Aglaostigma (Bivena) langei* (Konow, 1894)

Synonyms: *Rhogogastera langei* Konow, 1894a: 134–135; *Aglaostigma langei eichleri* Muehe, 1975: 239.

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Russia, Slovakia and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Chamerion angustifolium* (Linnaeus) and *Epilobium palustre* Linnaeus (Onagraceae) (Liston, 1995; Taeger, et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

127- *Macrophya (Macrophya) albicincta* (Schrank, 1776)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo albicincta* Schrank, 1776: 85; *Tenthredo albipes* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 371; *Tenthredo albipalpis* Schrank, 1802: 250–252; *Tenthredo lugubris* Lepelletier, 1823: 101; *Tenthredo luctuosa* Lepelletier, 1823: 103; *Tenthredo lugubris* Serville 1823: 42–43; *Tenthredo luctuosa* Serville, 1823: 44–45; *Macrophya leucopoda* Palma, 1861: 95–96; *Tenthredo (Macrophya) magnicornis* Eversmann in Kawall, 1864: 297; *Macrophya melanosoma* Rudow, 1871: 392; *Macrophya albicincta* var. *decipiens* Konow, 1884: 326; *Perineura crippae* De-Stefani, 1885: 185; *Macrophya albicincta* var. *candidata* Enslin, 1918: 726; *Macrophya albicincta* var. *agnani* Pic, 1948a: 4–5; *Macrophya albicincta* var. *berlandi* Pic, 1948a: 5.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999) and Lorestan province (Mallach, 1931).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Sambucus ebulus* Linnaeus, *S. nigra* Linnaeus, *S. racemosa* Linnaeus and *Viburnum* Linnaeus (Adoxaceae); *Valeriana officinalis* Linnaeus (Caprifoliaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

128- *Macrophya (Macrophya) alboannulata* (Costa, 1859)

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Gilan, Mazandaran (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press) and Golestan (Chevin, 1985) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Slovakia, Switzerland and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are oligophagus feeding on *Sambucus nigra*, *S. racemosa* and *S. ebulus* (Liston, 1995; Taeger et al., 1998; Lacourt, 1999).

129- *Macrophya (Macrophya) annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo annulata* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 373; *Tenthredo dorsigera* Rossi, 1790: vol. 2, 32; *Tenthredo similis* Spinola, 1808: 15–16; *Tenthredo (Allantus) neglecta* Klug, 1817a: 112–113; *Allantus dejectus* Norton, 1860: 249–250; *Macrophya annulata theresae* Pic, 1918: 4.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Schedl, 1987); Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press); Lorestan (Mallach, 1931) and Mazandaran (Mallach, 1931; Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain,

Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Origanum vulgare* Linnaeus (Lamiaceae); *Potentilla reptans* Linnaeus (Rosaceae), *Rosa* and *Rubus* (Taeger et al., 1998).

130- *Macrophya (Macrophya) arpaklena* Ushinskij, 1936

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran and Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

131- *Macrophya (Macrophya) blanda* (Fabricius, 1775)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo blanda* Fabricius, 1775: 323; *Tenthredo ligustrina* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 371; *Tenthredo cylindrica* Panzer, 1799: 71: 7; *Tenthredo albilabris* Klug, 1817a: 112; *Tenthredo lacrymosa* Lepeletier, 1823: 101; *Tenthredo lacrymosa* Serville, 1823: 43; *Tenthredo cognata* Fallén, 1829: 48; *Tenthredo nyctea* Fischer von Waldheim, 1843: 2; *Macrophya blanda* var. *brevicornis* Gradl, 1878: 239; *Macrophya blanda* var. *jacqueti* Pic, 1918: 3-4; *Macrophya albolapidaria* Kuznetsov-Ugamskij, 1927: 277-288; *Tenthredo reductenotata* Pic, 1928: 6.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Alborz (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press); Gilan (Zirngiebl, 1956; Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press); Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) and Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland,

Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

132- *Macrophya (Macrophya) carinthiaca* (Klug, 1817)

Synonym: *Tenthredo (Allantus) carinthiaca* Klug, 1817a: 118.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999) and Gilan province (Zirngiebl, 1956).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Netherlands, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown but *Geranium nodosum* Linnaeus, *G. phaeum* Linnaeus, *G. pratense* Linnaeus, *G. sanguineum* Linnaeus and *G. sylvaticum* Linnaeus (Geraniaceae) are hosts for adults (Taeger et al., 1998); Larvae feed on *G. sylvaticum* and *G. sanguineum* (Lacourt, 1999).

133- *Macrophya cyrus* Benson, 1954

Distribution in Iran: Southwest of Iran (Benson, 1954, 1968; Lacourt, 1999); Qazvin and Tehran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran and Turkey (Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Unknown.

134- *Macrophya diaphenia* Benson, 1968

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999); Northern of Iran, Lorestan (Benson, 1968), Alborz (Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press); Gilan, Qazvin, Mazandaran and Tehran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Benson 1968; Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

135- *Macrophya (Macrophya) diversipes* (Schrank, 1782)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo diversipes* Schrank, 1782: 289; *Tenthredo haematopus* Panzer, 1801: 81: 11–12; *Tenthredo ocreata* Panzer, 1804: 192; *Tenthredo rubripes* Drapiez, 1820: 122–123; *Tenthredo (Macrophya) corallipes* Eversmann, 1847: 41; *Macrophya flavipes* Tischbein, 1852a: 138; *Tenthredo halensis* Aichinger, 1870: 305, 310; *Macrophya haematopus* var. *immaculiventris* Costa, 1871: 19; *Macrophya eximia* Mocsáry, 1877: 87–88; *Macrophya caucasica* André, 1881c: 357; *Macrophya rubripes* André, 1881b: 589–590; *Macrophya saundersi* W.F. Kirby, 1886: 34; *Macrophya sanguinipes* Mocsáry, 1891: 155–156; *Macrophya dalmatina* Gasperini, 1891: 1; *Macrophya diversipes* var. *passerinii* Ghigi, 1905: 8, 28; *Macrophya diversipes* var. *feminina* Enslin, 1913: 140; *Macrophya diversipes* var. *masculina* Enslin, 1913: 140; *Macrophya diversipes* var. *maculativentris* Enslin, 1913: 140; *Macrophya diversipes* var. *nigritarsis* Enslin, 1913: 140.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Muche, 1972); Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999); Alborz, Gilan, Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Lorestan (Mallach, 1931) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Fragaria* sp. (Çalmaşur & Özbek, 2004a).

136- *Macrophya (Macrophya) longitarsis* Konow, 1898

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Gilan (Zirngiebl, 1956;

Khayrandish et al., in press); Lorestan (Mallach, 1931) and Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Transcaucasia and Iran (Benson, 1968).

Host plants: Unknown.

137- *Macrophya (Macrophya) montana* (Scopoli, 1763)

Synonym: *Tenthredo montana* Scopoli, 1763: 276–277.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details Lacourt (1999); Alborz, Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Chevin, 1985).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Rubus caesius* (Taeger et al., 1998); *Rubus* spp. (Lacourt, 1999).

138- *Macrophya oedipus* Benson, 1968

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Qazvin provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Greece and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

139- *Macrophya (Macrophya) ottomana* Mocsáry, 1881

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1954, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran and Turkey (Benson, 1968); Armenia, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Russia and Syria (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

140- *Macrophya (Macrophya) postica* (Brullé, 1832)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo postica* Brullé, 1832: 388–389; *Macrophya ratzeburgii* Tischbein, 1852c: 137; *Macrophya histrionica* Snellen van Vollenhoven, 1878: 155; *Macrophya postica* var. *nigripleuris* Enslin, 1913: 138; *Macrophya postica luteo maculata* Pic, 1918: 3; *Macrophya postica* var. *sex-maculata* Pic, 1918: 3.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Armenia, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lebanon, Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

141- *Macrophya (Pseudomacrophya) punctumalbum* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo Punctumalbum* Linnaeus, 1767: 924; *Tenthredo erythropus* Schrank, 1776: 86; *Tenthredo punctum* Fabricius, 1781: 415; *Tenthredo stellata* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 369.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1991, 1999); Mazandaran province (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Ligustrum vulgare* Linnaeus, *Fraxinus excelsior* Linnaeus (Oleaceae), *Crataegus* and *Quercus* (Taeger et al., 1998).

142- *Macrophya (Macrophya) rufipes* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo rufipes* Linnaeus, 1758: 557; *Tenthredo pavidata* Fabricius, 1775: 321; *Tenthredo dumetorum* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 373; *Tenthredo multicolor* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 370; *Tenthredo flavifasciata* Christ, 1791: 450–451; *Tenthredo rufipes* Christ, 1791: 439–440; *Tenthredo strigosa* Fabricius, 1798: 217; *Tenthredo citreipes* Lepeletier, 1823: 96; *Tenthredo citreipes* Serville, 1823: 37–38; *Allantus ione* Newman, 1837: 263; *Macrophya rufipes* var. *orientalis* Mocsáry, 1891: 156; *Macrophya rufipes* var. *muliebris* Enslin, 1913: 138; *Macrophya rufipes* var. *castiliensis* Enslin, 1914b: 166; *Macrophya rufipes* var. *reducta* Pic, 1918: 3; *Macrophya rufipes* var. *reductenotata* Pic, 1929: 3; *Macrophya rufipes* var. *diversereducta* Pic, 1929: 3.

Distribution in Iran: Southwest of Iran (Benson, 1954); Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Vitis vinifera* Linnaeus (Vitaceae), eggs of *M. rufipes* have observed on *Agrimonia* (Rosaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998); *Agrimonia eupatoria* (Linnaeus) (Lacourt, 1999).

143- *Macrophya (Macrophya) nr superba* Tischbein, 1852

Synonyms: *Macrophya erythropus* forma *croatica* Korlević, 1890: 200; *Macrophya flavipennis* Kriechbaumer, 1891: 190–191; *Macrophya erythropus* var. *fluminensis* Strobl, 1901: 77–78; *Macrophya superba* var. *nigricans* Enslin, 1913: 137.

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Georgia, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Turkey and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

144- *Rhogogaster (Cytisogaster) genistae* Benson, 1947

Synonyms: *Rhogogaster chambersi genistae* Benson, 1947: 98–99; *Rhogogaster genistae viridifrons* Mucho, 1973: 87–88.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden and Switzerland (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Cytisus scoparius* (Linnaeus), *Lembotropis nigricans* (Linnaeus), *Genista tinctoria* Linnaeus and *G. germanica* Linnaeus (Fabaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

145- *Rhogogaster (Rhogogaster) viridis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo viridis* Linné, 1758: 557; *Tenthredo viridis* Poda, 1761: 103; *Tenthredo straminea* Schrank, 1776: 85–86; *Tenthredo hebraica* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 363–364; *Tenthredo annalicornis* Gmelin, 1790: 2667; *Tenthredo interrupta* Fabricius, 1804: 40; *Tenthredo (Allantus) scalaris* Klug, 1817b: 194–195; *Tenthredo pictipes* Förster, 1850: 287–288; *Tenthredo chloros* Rudow, 1871: 387–388; *Rhogogaster viridis* var. *sibirica* Enslin, 1912b: 93; *Rhogogaster viridis* var. *melanonota* Enslin, 1912b: 93; *Rhogogaster viridis* var. *lapponica* Enslin, 1918: 722; *Rhogogaster viridis* var. *nigroscutellata* Forsius, 1918a: 150; *Rhogogaster ruga* MacGillivray, 1923b: 160;

Rhogogaster respectus MacGillivray, 1923c: 165; *Rhogogaster viridis* forma *montana* Betrem, 1933: 377–378.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are polyphagous feeding on *Circaea* Tournefort (Onagraceae), *Frangula alnus* Miller (Rhamnaceae), *Populus*, *Quercus*, *Ranunculus* Linnaeus (Ranunculaceae), *Rubus*, *Stellaria*, *Betula*, *Alnus incana*, *Salix caprea*, *S. viminalis* Linnaeus, *Vicia cracca* Linnaeus (Fabaceae), *Filipendula ulmaria* (Taeger et al., 1998).

146- *Sciapteryx lactipennis* Konow, 1903

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Konow, 1903; Kuznetzov-Ugamskij, 1929; Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Russia (Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Iran (Konow, 1903).

Host plants: Unknown.

147- *Sciapteryx nigriventris* André, 1882

Synonym: *Sciapteryx costalis vernalis* Kuznetzov-Ugamskij, 1929: 54–55.

Distribution in Iran: Kermanshah province (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Iran (Chevin, 1985).

Host plants: Unknown.

148- *Tenthredo (Tenthredella) araxana* Mocsáry, 1909

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Mocsáry, 1909).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

149- *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) arcuata* Forster, 1771

Synonyms: *Allantus arcuatus* var. *alpigena* Heller & Dalla Torre, 1883: 30, 40; *Allantus clypealis* Konow, 1888a: 220; *Tenthredo arcuata* var. *melanoxyston* Enslin, 1912b: 87; *Allantus arcuatus* ab. *nigrotegulatus* Csiki, 1923: 103, 107; *Allantus arcuatus* var. *similans* Zirngiebl, 1949: 285, 290; *Allantus sulphuripes* var. *tegularis* Zirngiebl, 1949: 289; *Tenthredo arcuata* forma *montana* Muche, 1971: 54.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Zirngiebl, 1949; Benson, 1959, 1968; Blank, 1996).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Trifolium repens* Linnaeus (Fabaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

150- *Tenthredo (Cephaledo) bifascita* O. F. Muller, 1766

Synonym: *Tenthredo vidua* var. *palestina* Pic, 1948a: 10.

Distribution in Iran: Qazvin, Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Bulgaria,

Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Aegopodium?* Linnaeus (Apiaceae) (Liston, 1995).

151- *Tenthredo caligator* Eversmann, 1847

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) caligator* Eversmann, 1847: 47; *Tenthredo nigritarsis* Puls, 1870: 152; *Tenthredo morawitzi* Jakowlew, 1888: 372.

Distribution in Iran: Lorestan province (Mallach, 1931).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia and Georgia (Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Iran (Mallach, 1931).

Host plants: Unknown.

152- *Tenthredo (Elinora) caspia* (André, 1881)

Synonym: *Allantus caspius* André, 1881d: 400.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1946, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Russia and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

153- *Tenthredo (Maculedo) cinctipleuris* (Enslein, 1910)

Synonym: *Allantus cinctipleuris* Enslin, 1910: 343, 363–364.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger, 1988a); Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Alborz (Benson, 1968; Chevin, 1985; Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Georgia, Iran and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

154- *Tenthredo (Cephaledo) costata* Klug, 1817

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) costata* Klug, 1817a: 142–143; *Tenthredo (Allantus) sareptana* Eversmann, 1847: 39–40; *Allantus faustus*

W.F. Kirby, 1882: 245; *Allantus subcostatus* Jakowlew, 1888: 374–375; *Allantus graecus* Konow, 1888a: 216; *Allantus parnasius* Konow, 1888a: 214–216; *Allantus violaceipennis* Costa, 1890: 16, pl. III; *Allantus kiefferi* Konow, 1899c: 363–364; *Allantus kietteri* var. *cilix* Enslin, 1910: 351; *Tenthredo kiefferi* var. *lugubrata* Enslin, 1914a: 57; *Allantus costatus* var. *obscurus* Zirngiebl, 1937b: 347; *Tenthredo costata* ab. *nigradorsata* Čingovski, 1958: 164–165, 178.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Armenia, Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Chondrilla* Linnaeus (Asteraceae) (Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993).

Remarks: Benson (1968) listed Iran under the general distribution of *T. costata* but he did not present detailed collection data for this country. So occurrence of this species in Iran need to be re-confirmed.

155- *Tenthredo (Zonuleda) distinguenda* (Stein, 1885)

Synonym: *Allantus distinguendus* Stein, 1885: 117.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger, 1991); Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999; Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Gilan province (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Iran, Italy, Macedonia, Netherlands, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

156- *Tenthredo (Cephaledo) excellens* (Konow, 1886)

Synonyms: *Allantus excellens* Konow, 1886b: 17; *Allantus persa* Konow, 1888a: 212–213; *Allantus persa* var. *mandibularis* Enslin, 1910: 344, 364; *Tenthredo persa* var. *caja* Enslin, 1912a: 104.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Konow, 1888; Enslin, 1910; Taeger, 1988b, 1992; Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993); Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999); Gilan, Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press); Khorasan, Semnan (Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Mazandaran (Taeger & Blank, 2011; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Georgia, Greece, Iran, Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Turkey, Turkmenistan and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

157- *Tenthredo (Zonuledo) flavipennis* Brullé, 1832

Synonym: *Allantus frivaldszkyi* Mocsáry, 1879: 118–119; *Allantus lautus* Konow, 1891: 47; *Allantus luminosus* Konow, 1899a: 204–205.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Gilan, Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Mazandaran (Taeger & Blank, 2011) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Slovakia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

158- *Tenthredo (Elinora) longipes* (Konow, 1886)

Synonyms: *Allantus longipes* Konow, 1886b: 20–21; *Allantus shestoperovi* Ushinskij, 1936: 104, 110–111; *Cuneala tricolor* Zirngiebl, 1956: 322–325.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger, 1988a); Northern of Iran

(Lacourt, 1999; Blank & Taeger, 2006; Taeger & Blank, 2011); Gilan (Zirngiebl, 1956; Blank, 1996) and Mazandaran (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan, Iran, Russia and Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown. Adults were collected from flowers of *Ranunculus* in woodland and in forest clearings (Benson, 1968).

159- *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) marginella* Fabricius, 1793

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran and Tehran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Macedonia, Netherlands, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae are polyphagous feeding on *Melissa officinalis* Linnaeus, *Mentha piperita* Linnaeus, *Ocimum basilicum* Linnaeus, *Lycopus* Linnaeus and *Origanum vulgare* Linnaeus (Lamiaceae), *Tussilago* Linnaeus (Asteraceae) and *Plantago* (Taeger et al., 1998).

160- *Tenthredo (Eurogaster) mioceras* (Enslin, 1912)

Synonyms: *Tenthredella mesomelas* var. *mioceras* Enslin, 1912b: 49; *Tenthredo mioceras* Benson, 1943: 138; *Tenthredo mesomelas montana* Pasteels, 1946: 246.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Lorestan province (Mallach, 1931).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Oriental (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, China, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain,

Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Heracleum* Linnaeus (Apiaceae), *Ranunculus*, *Atropa belladonna* Linnaeus (Solanaceae), *Dryopteris*, *Senecio ovatus* (Gartner, Meyer & Scherbius) (Asteraceae)

Lycopus Linnaeus (Lamiaceae), *Polygonum* and *Rubus* (Taeger et al., 1998).

161- *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) notha* Klug, 1817

Synonym: *Tenthredo (Allantus) notha* Klug, 1817a: 140.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Vicia cracca* (Taeger et al., 1998), *Trifolium repens*, *T. pratense*, *Vicia cracca* (Lacourt, 1999).

Remark: Lacourt (1999) is not a primary source so this record is not confirmed.

162- *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) pamyrensis* Jakowlew, 1888

Distribution in Iran: Semnan province (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); China, Iran, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Salix* sp. (Lacourt, 1999).

163- *Tenthredo (Elinora) persica* (André, 1882)

Synonyms: *Allantus persicus* André, 1882: 440-441; *Tenthredo coniensis* Enslin, 1914a: 55-56; *Allantus (Tenthredo) kareli* Muehe, 1962: 17-19; *Allantus (Tenthredo) kareli forma maculatus* Muehe, 1962: 19.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1998, 1999); Alborz (Khayrandish et al., in press); Qazvin (Benson, 1968; Khayrandish et al., in press) and Tehran (André, 1882; Khayrandish et al., in press) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Russia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on ?*Lepidium* (Lacourt, 1999).

164- *Tenthredo (Elinora) radoszkowskii* (André, 1881)

Synonyms: *Macrophya radoszkowskii* André, 1881b: 591; *Allantus atratus* André, 1883: 206; *Allantus confinis* Konow, 1886b: 21; *Allantus parviceps* Konow, 1898a: 329.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Taeger, 1988a); Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999; Blank & Taeger, 2006).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Iran (Blank & Taeger, 2006).

Host plants: Unknown.

165- *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) scrophulariae* Linnaeus, 1758

Synonyms: *Allantus scrophulariae* var. *joannis* Pic, 1926: 11; *Allantus scrophulariae* var. *repartitus* Pic, 1926: 11; *Allantus scrophulariae* var. *morvandicus* Pic, 1926: 11; *Allantus scrophulariae* var. *branensis* Pic, 1926: 11.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger, 1988b) and Mazandaran province (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland,

Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Scrophularia nodosa* Linnaeus, *S. auriculata* Linnaeus, *Verbascum* spp. (Scrophulariaceae) (Lacourt, 1999), *Verbascum nigrum* Linnaeus, *Scrophularia auriculata*, *S. nodosa*, *S. umbrosa* Dumortier (Taeger et al., 1998).

166- *Tenthredo (Paratenthredo) talyshensis* Zhelochovtsev, 1988

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Benson, 1968; Taeger, 1991; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Turkey and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

167- *Tenthredo (Tenthredo) variabilis* (Mocsáry, 1909)

Synonyms: *Allantus variabilis* Mocsáry, 1909: 26; *Tenthredo variana* Benson, 1930: 107; *Tenthredo carolinae* Zirngiebl, 1937c: 351-352.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran, Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

168- *Tenthredo (Maculedo) vespiformis* Schrank, 1781

Synonyms: *Tenthredo pallicornis* Fabricius, 1798: 215; *Tenthredo vespoides* Lepeletier, 1823: 73; *Tenthredo bella* Lepeletier, 1823: 73; *Tenthredo vespoides* Serville, 1823: 18; *Tenthredo bella* Serville, 1823: 18; *Allantus theresae* Pic, 1925: 15; *Tenthredo pallicornis* var. *separates* Pic, 1926: 12; *Tenthredo pallicornis* var. *immaculatus* Pic, 1926: 11; *Tenthredo pallicornis* var. *bimaculiventris* Pic, 1926: 11.

Distribution in Iran: Tehran province (Abai, 2009).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain,

Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

169- *Tenthredo (Maculedo) vestita* André, 1881

Synonyms: *Tenthredo caspica* Mocsáry, 1883: 7; *Tenthredo laeta* Konow, 1886c: 41; *Allantus limbiferus* Mocsáry, 1891: 156; *Tenthredella celsia* Enslin, 1912a: 104; *Tenthredo vestita* var. *striata* Enslin, 1920: 18, 83; *Tenthredo vestita* var. *striata* Enslin, 1920: 18, 83; *Tenthredo vestita* var. *strigata* Enslin, 1920: 18.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Golestan (Chevin, 1985; Lacourt, 1999) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Turkey, Transcaucasia and Iran (Lacourt, 1999).

Host plants: Unknown.

170- *Tenthredo (Zonuledo) zonula* Klug, 1817

Synonyms: *Tenthredo (Allantus) zonula* Klug, 1817a: 137; *Allantus similis* Mocsáry, 1880: 270–271; *Allantus calcaratus* André, 1881b: 595; *Allantus scutellaris* Konow, 1898b: 325, 327.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Mocsáry, 1880; Enslin, 1910; Benson, 1955; Dadurian, 1962; Taeger, 1991, 1992); Northern of Iran (Lacourt, 1999); Alborz, Qazvin (Khayrandish et al., in press); Fars, Khorasan, Lorestan and Zanjan (Taeger & Blank, 2011) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Hypericum perforatum* Linnaeus (Hypericaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

171- *Tenthredopsis humerosa* Konow, 1898

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Konow, 1898); East Azerbaijan province (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

172- *Tenthredopsis litterata* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo litterata* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 370; *Tenthredo cordata* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 368; *Tenthredo thoracica* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 376; *Tenthredo varia* Gmelin, 1790: 2665; *Tenthredo flavipes* Christ, 1791: 445; *Tenthredo cruciata* Christ, 1791: 448; *Tenthredo dimidiata* Fabricius, 1804: 42; *Tenthredo rubiginosa* Drapiez, 1819: 202–204; *Tenthredo microcephala* Lepeletier, 1823: 80–81; *Tenthredo microcephala* Serville, 1823: 25; *Tenthredo caliginosa* Stephens, 1829: 337; *Tenthredo analis* Stephens, 1829: 337; *Tenthredo caliginosa* Stephens, 1835: 78; *Tenthredo femoralis* Stephens, 1835: 80; *Tenthredo analis* Stephens, 1835: 80; *Tenthredo orbitalis* Dietrich, 1868: 354–355; *Tenthredopsis nigriceps* Cameron, 1881: 569–570; *Tenthredopsis nigronotatus* Cameron, 1881: 566–567; *Thomsonia thomsoni* Konow, 1884: 328, 333; *Tenthredopsis thomsoni* var. *concolor* Konow, 1887b: 281; *Tenthredopsis thomsoni* var. *nigripes* Konow, 1890a: 70; *Tenthredopsis pallida* Konow, 1896a: 316; *Tenthredopsis sordida* var. *pallida* Konow, 1896b: 50; *Tenthredopsis litterata* var. *bicolor* Enslin, 1913: 102; *Tenthredopsis litterata* var. *melaena* Enslin, 1918: 723; *Tenthredopsis litterata* var. *variana* Enslin, 1918: 723; *Tenthredopsis litterata* ab. *albanica* Csiki, 1923: 103, 108; *Tenthredopsis litterata* var. *subcarpathica* Gregor, 1927: 31, 38; *Tenthredopsis carbonaria* var. *medionotata* Pic, 1948b: 5.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Agrostis* Linnaeus, *Dactylis glomerata* Linnaeus and *Calamagrostis epigejos* (Linnaeus) (Poaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

173- *Tenthredopsis nigella* Konow, 1891

Distribution in Iran: Alborz and Mazandaran provinces (Khayrandish et al., in press).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia, Macedonia, Russia and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011); Yugoslavia, Asiatic Turkey and Transcaucasia (Benson, 1968; Liston, 1995).

Host plants: Unknown.

174- *Tenthredopsis ornata* (Serville, 1823)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo ornata* Serville, 1823: 21; *Tenthredo neglecta* Serville, 1823: 22; *Tenthredo ornata* Lepeletier, 1823: 77; *Tenthredo neglecta* Lepeletier, 1823: 77-78; *Perineura excisa* Thomson, 1870: 301; *Thomsonia excisa* var. *binotata* Konow, 1884: 333; *Tenthredopsis excisa* var. *atriscutis* Enslin, 1918: 725.

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Lacourt, 1999); Alborz, Gilan, Mazandaran (Khayrandish et al., in press) and Golestan (Chevin, 1985) provinces.

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Brachypodium silvaticum* (Hudson) (Poaceae) (Lacourt, 1999).

175- *Tenthredopsis sororia* Konow, 1898

Distribution in Iran: Iran without locality details (Konow, 1898).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Armenia and Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

176- *Tenthredopsis tessellata* (Klug, 1817)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *tessellata* Klug, 1817b: 200-201; *Tenthredo* (*Tenthredo*) *ischiadica* Eversmann, 1847: 48; *Tenthredo* (*Macrophya*) *ischiadica* Eversmann in Kawall, 1864: 298; *Perineura cylindrica* Rudow, 1871: 390-391; *Tenthredopsis tessellata* var. *alboplagiata* Konow, 1890a: 78; *Tenthredopsis albata* Konow, 1904b: 267-268; *Tenthredopsis tessellata* var. *nigratileuris* Enslin, 1913: 119; *Tenthredopsis tessellata* var. *nigratilobis* Enslin, 1913: 119; *Tenthredopsis tessellata* var. *nigratiscutis* Enslin, 1913: 119.

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Benson, 1968; Lacourt, 1999).

General distribution: Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland and Turkey (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Aira* sp. Linnaeus and *Deschampsia cespitosa* (Linnaeus) (Poaceae) (Taeger et al., 1998).

IX- Family Xiphydriidae

177- *Xiphydria prolongata* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Synonyms: *Tenthredo prolongata* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785: 379; *Sirex dromedarius* Fabricius, 1787: 258; *Xyphidria fasciata* Lepeletier, 1823: 3.

Distribution in Iran: Gilan province (Ebrahimi, 1995; Modarres Awal, 1997).

General distribution: Palaearctic, Nearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great

Britain, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, USA and Yugoslavia (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Larvae feed on *Ulmus*, *Populus*, *Salix caprea* Linnaeus (Taeger et al., 1998).

178- *Xiphydria scutellata* Konow, 1897

Distribution in Iran: Northern of Iran (Konow, 1897, 1898; Gussakovskij, 1935; Ushinskij, 1936; Maa, 1949).

General distribution: West Palaearctic (Taeger et al., 2010); Azerbaijan and Iran (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Host plants: Unknown.

Discussion

This is the first faunistic overview on Symphyta in Iran. According to the literatures 178 species of Symphyta have been reported from Iran of which six species need to be re-confirmed (Abai 2009, Abai & Moghadam 1993, Beneš 1981, Beneš & Abai 1991, Benson 1968, Chevin 1985, Ebrahimi 1995, Farahbakhsh 1961, Gussakovskij 1935, Khayrandish et al. in press, 2015, Koch 1988, Lacourt 1999, Mallach 1931, Modarres Awal 1997, Shahmohammadi et al. 2008, Shinohara 1997, Taeger 2002, Taeger and Blank 2011, Wei 2008, Zirngiebl 1956). Among the recorded species, 12 species (*Arge persica*, *Sterictiphora caspica*, *Allantus zonarius*, *Allantus alborzanus*, *Allantus geminus*, *Ametastegia persica*, *Scolioneura hyrcana*, *Craesus medunai*, *Craesus persicus*, *Macrophya diaphenia*, *Tenthredo araxana*, *Tenthredopsis humerosa*) seems to be endemic as they currently only recorded from Iran. Most species are belonging to family Tenthredinidae (131 species) followed by Argidae (19 species), Cephidae (9 species), Megalodontesidae (7 species), Cimbicidae (4 species), Pamphilidae (3 species), Orussidae, Siricidae and Xiphydriidae (each with 2 species).

Iran is located between the Western and Eastern parts of Palaearctic region but Iranian fauna of Symphyta is very similar to countries of West Palaearctic as follows: Russia (117 species) (Zhelochovtsev & Zinovjev, 1993; Taeger & Blank, 2011), Germany and Italy (106 species) (Taeger et al., 1998; Taeger & Blank, 2011), Austria (105 species) (Taeger & Blank, 2011), France (100 species) (Berland, 1947; Lacourt, 1999; Taeger & Blank, 2011), Bulgaria (93 species) (Taeger & Blank, 2011), Turkey (91 species) (Benson, 1968; Çalmaşur & Özbek, 2004a, 2004b; Taeger & Blank, 2011), Spain (90 species) (Taeger & Blank, 2011), Great Britain (87 species) (Benson, 1951, 1952, 1958; Taeger & Blank, 2011) and Greece (77 species) (Taeger & Blank, 2011) but common species with China and Japan from East Palaearctic are much less than countries of West Palaearctic with 33 and 18 species, respectively. The similarity of Iran's fauna with countries of other regions are recorded as: USA (in Nearctic) (32 species), Chile (in Neotropic) (5 species), South Africa (in Afrotropic) (2 species), India (in Oriental) (2 species) and Australia (in Australasian) (5 species) (Taeger & Blank, 2011).

Tenthredinidae with 38 genera (63.33%) is the most genera-rich family followed by Cephidae with 6 (10%) genera. Also Tenthredinidae with 131 species (73.59%) is the most species-rich family followed by Argidae with 18 species (10.11%) (Table 1). Gilan province consist of 37 genera and 77 species of symphyta followed by Mazandaran with 31 and 71, and Alborz province with 23 genera and 42 species comparing to other provinces in Iran (Table 2). Since Iran is a large country with different climate zones, some other new species records and new taxa will probably be founded from different parts of the country, and thus this checklist will need to be periodically updated.

Table 1. Frequency and abundance of sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) in Iran.

Family	Genera		Species	
	Number	Percentage	Number	percentage
Argidae	4	6.66	18	10.11
Cephidae	6	10	9	5.05
Cimbicidae	3	5	4	2.25
Megalodontesidae	1	1.66	7	3.93
Orussidae	2	3.33	2	1.13
Pamphiliidae	3	5	3	1.68
Siricidae	2	3.33	2	1.13
Tenthredinidae	38	63.33	131	73.59
Xiphydriidae	1	1.66	2	1.13

Table 2. Frequency and abundance of sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) in different provinces of Iran.

Iranian Provinces	Number of taxa		
	Family	Genus	Species
Alborz	5	23	42
East Azerbaijan	4	5	5
Fars	4	5	5
Gilan	8	37	77
Golestan	3	9	11
Hamadan	1	1	1
Isfahan	1	2	3
Kermanshah	1	2	2
Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad	1	1	1
Kordistan	1	2	2
Lorestan	6	10	16
Markazi	2	4	4
Mazandaran	5	31	71
Qazvin	4	15	29
Razavi Khorasan	2	3	4
Semnan	1	1	2
Sistan & Baluchestan	2	2	2
South Khorasan	1	1	1
Tehran	3	13	17
West Azerbaijan	2	2	2
Zanjan	1	1	1

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Abai, M. (1994) The first record of *Fenusa ulmi* in Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 61(1-2), 35, 133.
- Abai, M. (2009) *Pests of forest trees and shrubs of Iran*. Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran.
- Abai, M. & Moghadam, M. (1993) First report on the occurrence of black sawfly (*Tomostethus nigritus* subsp. *clavipennis* Enslin) in Iran.

- Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 60(1-2), 30, 94.
- Aichinger, V.V. (1870) Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Hymenopteren-Fauna Tirols. *Zeitschrift des Ferdinandeums für Tirol und Vorarlberg*, 3 (15), 293-330.
- André, E. (1879) *Species des Hyménoptères d'Europe & d'Algérie*. Beaune (Côte-d'Or), 1[1879-1882] (3), CXXXIII-CXLVIII, 1-48, catalogue 1-8.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.10281>
- André, E. (1880) *Species des Hyménoptères d'Europe & d'Algérie*. Beaune (Côte-d'Or), 1[1879-1882](4), CXLIX-CXCVI, 49-96. [01.01.1880].
- André, E. (1881a) Notes hyménoptérologiques. II. Catalogue raisonné des Tenthredines recueillies en Syrie et en Palestine en 1880 par M. Elzéar Abeille de Perrin. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (6), 1, 345-362.
- André, E. (1881b) *Species des Hyménoptères d'Europe & d'Algérie*. Beaune (Côte-d'Or), 1[1879-1882](11), 565-596.
- André, E. (1881c) *Species des Hyménoptères d'Europe & d'Algérie*. Beaune (Côte-d'Or), 1[1879-1882](8), 301-380, catalogue 37-48.
- André, E. (1881d) *Species des Hyménoptères d'Europe & d'Algérie*. Beaune (Côte-d'Or), 1[1879-1882] (9), 381-484, catalogue 49-56.
- André, E. (1882) Notes hyménoptérologiques. III. Description de Quelques Tenthredines orientales inédites. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France*, (6) 1[1881], 437-443.
- André, E. (1883) Description d'une Tenthredine inédite de la faune de Sarepta. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (6), *Bulletin*, 3, 206.
- Ashmead, W.H. (1900) Order Hymenoptera. In: Smith, J.B., *Insects of New Jersey. A list of the species occurring in New Jersey, with notes on those of economic importance. Twenty Seventh Annual Report of the New Jersey State Board of Agriculture, Supplement*, Trenton, N. J., 1899, pp. 510-613.
- Ashmead, W.H. (1903) Two new phytophagous Hymenoptera. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 35(8), 233.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent35233-8>
- Behdad, E. (1982) *Pests of field crop in Iran*. Plant Pests and Diseases Research Institute, Tehran. [In Persian]
- Behdad, E. (1984) *Pests of fruit crops*. Ibid, Tehran. [In Persian]
- Behdad, E. (1988) *Pests and diseases of forest trees and shrubs of Iran*. Ibid, Tehran. [In Persian]
- Beneš, K., Abai, M. (1991) A new species of *Croesus* injurious to birch in Iran (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Acta Entomologica Bohemoslovaca*, 88, 253-263.
- Beneš, K. (1981) *Croesus persicus* sp. n. from Iran (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Acta Entomologica Bohemoslovaca*, 78, 177-182.
- Benson, R.B. (1930) Nine sawflies requiring new names. *The Entomologist*, 63, 107.
- Benson, R.B. (1943) The green British species of *Tenthredo* (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *The Entomologist*, 76, 133-144.
- Benson, R.B. (1947) A new British sawfly (Hym.: Tenthredinidae) related to *Rhogogaster picta* (Klug). *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine, Fourth Series*, 83(8), 96-99.
- Benson, R.B. (1951) Hymenoptera, Symphyta. Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects, 6 (2a), 1-49.
- Benson, R.B. (1952) Hymenoptera, Symphyta. Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects, 6 (2b), 51-137.
- Benson, R.B. (1954) Some sawflies of the European Alps and the Mediterranean region (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History). Entomology series*, 3 (7), 267-295.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.1054>
- Benson, R.B. (1955) The sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) of Israel. *Bulletin of the Research Council of Israel*, 4(4), 351-356.
- Benson, R.B. (1958) Hymenoptera, Symphyta. Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects, 6(2c), 139-252 + [6] pp.
- Benson, R.B. (1961) A new European species of *Nematus* (Hym., Tenthredinidae) on *Polygonum*. *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine, Fourth Series*, 96[1960], 228-229.
- Benson, R.B. (1962) A revision of the Athaliini (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History). Entomology series*, 11, 333-382.
- Benson, R.B. (1968) Hymenoptera from Turkey, Symphyta. *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History). Entomology series*, 22 (4),

- 111–207.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.9952>
- Berland, L. (1947) Hyménoptères Tenthredoïdes. *Faune de France*, 47, 1–493.
- Blank, S.M. (1996) Revision of the sawflies described by Lothar Zirngiebl. (Preliminary studies for a catalogue of Symphyta, part 2.) (Insecta: Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Spixiana. Zeitschrift für Zoologie*, 19 (2), 195–219.
- Blank, S.M., Shinohara, A. & Taeger, A. (1998) Revisionary Notes on Pamphiliid Sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Pamphiliidae). Preliminary studies for a catalogue of Symphyta, part 3. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 45 (1), 17–31.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mmnd.19980450104>
- Blank, S.M. & Taeger, A. (2006) Taxonomy and Evolution of *Tenthredo* (*Elinora*) Species Similar to *T. dahlii* and *T. koehleri* (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). In: Blank, S.M., Schmidt, S. & Taeger, A. (eds.) *Recent Sawfly Research – Synthesis and Prospects*. Goecke and Evers, Keltern, pp. 199–227.
- Boheman, C.H. (1852) Entomologiska Anteckningar under en resa i Sörda Sverige. 1851. *Kongl. Vetenskaps-Academiens Handlingar, För År 1852*, 53–210.
- Boie, F. (1848) Entomologisch biologische Notizen. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 9, 338–341.
- Bremi-Wolf, J.J. (1849) Beschreibung einiger Hymenopteren, die ich für noch unbeschriebene und unpublicirt halte. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 10(3), 92–96.
- Brischke, C.G.A. (1850) *Nematus helicinus* Dahlb. n. sp. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 11(12), 409–411.
- Brischke, C.G.A. (1883a) Beobachtungen über die Arten der Blatt- und Holzwespen von C. G. A. Brischke, Hauptlehrer a. D. in Langfuhr und Dr. Gustav Zaddach weiland Professor in Königsberg. Zweite Abtheilung. *Schriften der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Danzig, N. S.*, 5[1881–1883] (4), 201–328.
- Brischke, C.G.A. (1883b) Beobachtungen über die Arten der Blatt- und Holzwespen von C. G. A. Brischke, Hauptlehrer a.D. in Langfuhr und Dr. Gustav Zaddach Professor in Königsberg, mitgeteilt von Brischke aus Zaddach's Manuscripten. *Schriften der physikalisch-ökonomischen Gesellschaft zu Königsberg*, 23[1882], 127–200.
- Brischke, C.G.A. (1884) Beobachtungen über die Arten der Blatt- und Holzwespen von C. G. A. Brischke, Hauptlehrer a. D. in Langfuhr und Dr. Gustav Zaddach, Professor in Königsberg, mitgeteilt von Brischke aus Zaddach's Manuscripten. (Schluss). *Schriften der physikalisch-ökonomischen Gesellschaft zu Königsberg*, 24[1883], 121–173.
- Brischke, C.G.A. (1885) Nachtrag zu den Beobachtungen über die Blatt- und Holzwespen. *Schriften der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Danzig, N. S.*, 6[1884–1887] (2), 243–251.
- Brullé, A. (1832) Zoologie. Deuxième Section. Des animaux articulés. *Expédition scientifique de Morée. Section des sciences physiques*, 3 (1), 64–395.
- Brullé, A. (1846) *Histoire naturelle des Insectes. Hyménoptères*. (ed. Lepeletier de Saint-Fargeau), Vol. 4. Paris. pp. 1–680.
- Burggraaf-Van Nierop, Y.D. & Achterberg, C. Van (1990) The Cephidae and Argidae of the Netherlands (Hymenoptera). *Zoologische Bijdragen*, 39, 3–66.
- Çalmaşur, Ö. & Özbek, H.A. (2004a) Contribution to the Knowledge of the Fauna of Tenthredinidae (Symphyta: Hymenoptera) of Turkey Part I: The Subfamily Tenthredininae. *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 28, 37–54.
- Çalmaşur, Ö. & Özbek, H.A. (2004b) Contribution to the Knowledge of the Fauna of Tenthredinidae (Symphyta: Hymenoptera) of Turkey Part II: The Subfamilies Blennocampinae, Dolerinae, Nematinae and Selandriinae. *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 28, 55–71.
- Cameron, P. (1875) Description of a new species of *Nematus* from Corsica. *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 12(133), 9.
- Cameron, P. (1877) Descriptions of three new British saw-flies. *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 14(163), 155–157.
- Cameron, P. (1881) Notes on Hymenoptera, with descriptions of new species. *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London for the Year, 1881* (4), 555–577.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2311.1881.Tb00881.x>

- Cameron, P. (1882a) Notes on Tenthredinidae. *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 18(213), 193-195.
- Cameron, P. (1882b) XXIII. Descriptions of ten new species of *Nematus* from Britain. *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London for the Year 1882*, (4), 531-540.
- Cameron, P. (1885) *A monograph of the British phytophagous Hymenoptera (Tenthredo, Sirex and Cynips, Linné)*. London, vol. 2, pp. i-vi + 1-233.
- Cameron, P. (1902) Descriptions of new genera and species of Hymenoptera collected by Major C. G. Nurse at Deesa, Simla and Ferozepore. Part II. *Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society*, 14(3), 419-449.
- Cavalcaselle, B. (1968) Contributo alla conoscenza di *Stauronematus compressicornis* (F.) (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Pubblicazioni del Centro di Sperimentazione Agricola e Forestale Roma*, 9, 235-280.
- Chevin, H. (1985) Contribution à la faune de l'Iran 26. Hyménoptères Symphytes. *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie. Nouvelle Série*, 1[1984], 347-351.
- Christ, J.L. (1791) *Naturgeschichte, Classification und Nomenclatur der Insecten vom Bienen, Wespen und Ameisengeschlecht; als der fünften Klasse fünfte Ordnung des Linneischen Natursystems von den Insecten: Hymenoptera. Mit häutigen Flügeln*. Hermannsche Buchhandlung, Frankfurt am Main, pp. 1-535.
- Čingovski, J. (1958) Zweiter Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Blattwespenfauna von Mazedonien. *Acta Musei Macedonici Scientiarum Naturalium*, 5(10), 163-177.
- Cobelli, R. (1892) Quattro nuove specie di Imenotteri. *Verhandlungen der kaiserlich-königlichen zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien, Wissenschaftliche Abhandlungen*, 42(1), 67-72.
- Contarini, N.B. (1852) Sopra di un Gallinsetto degli foglie del Salice. *Memorie del Reale Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti*, 4, 115-131.
- Costa, A. (1852) *Storia della Tentredine produttrice delle galle delle foglie del Salcio (Salix Russelliana)*. Napoli, 17 pp.
- Costa, A. (1858) *Ricerche entomologiche sopra i Monti Partenii Nel Principato Ulteriore. Stamperia e calcografia Vico Freddo Pignasecca, Napoli*, 29 + [1] pp.
- Costa, A. (1859a) *Fauna del Regno di Napoli. Imenotteri. Parte III. – Trivellanti Sessiliventri. [Tentredinidei]*. Antonio Cons, Napoli, [1859-1860], pp. 1-116.
- Costa, A. (1859b) *Fauna del Regno di Napoli. Imenotteri. Parte III. – Trivellanti Sessiliventri. [Cimbicidae]*. Antonio Cons, Napoli, [1859-1860], pp. 1-8
- Costa, A. (1860) *Fauna del Regno di Napoli. Imenotteri. Parte III. – Trivellanti Sessiliventri. [Lididei, Cefidei, Siricidae, Orissidei]*. Antonio Cons, Napoli, [1859-1860], pp. 1-4 + 1-12 + 1-6 + 1-6.
- Costa, A. (1864) Articolo 2.° Specie immesse per effetto di doni o cambii. *Annuario del Museo Zoologico della R. Università di Napoli*, 2[1862], 94-118.
- Costa, A. (1869) Articolo 1.° Acquisiti fatti durante l'anno 1865. *Annuario del Museo Zoologico della R. Università di Napoli*, 5(1865), 8-22.
- Costa, A. (1871) Articolo 1.° Acquisiti fatti durante l'anno 1866. *Annuario del Museo Zoologico della R. Università di Napoli*, 6[1866], 8-26.
- Costa, A. (1875) Relazione di un viaggio per l'Egitto, la Palestina e le Coste della Turchia asiatica per ricerche zoologiche. *Atti della Reale Accademia delle Scienze Fisiche e Matematiche*, 7[1878] (2), 1-40.
- Costa, A. (1882) Rapporto preliminare e sommario sulle ricerche zoologiche fatte in Sardegna durante la primavera del 1882. *Rendiconto dell' Accademia delle Scienze Fisiche e Matematiche. 1. Ser*, 21, 189-201.
- Costa, A. (1890) *Miscellanea Entomologica. [Reprint from:] Atti della Reale Accademia delle Scienze Fisiche e Matematiche di Napoli*, 5, 1-19.
- Costa, A. (1894) Prospetto degli Imenotteri Italiani. III, Tenthredinidei e Siricidae. *Atti della Reale Accademia delle Scienze Fisiche e Matematiche*, 3, 1-290.
- Cresson, E.T. (1880) Descriptions of new North American Hymenoptera in the collection of the American Entomological Society. *Transactions of the American Entomological Society*, 8, 1-52.

- Csiki, E. (1923) Csiki Ernő állattani kutatásai Albániában. — *Explorationes zoologicae ab E. Csiki in Albania peractae*. VIII. Levéldarazsak. — Tenthredinoidea. *A Magyar Tudományos Akadémia Balkán-Kutatásainak tudományos eredményei*, 1[1922], 103–108.
- Dadurian, H.B. (1962) On the Sawflies and the Horntails of Armenian SSR (Insecta: Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Academy of Sciences of Armenian SSR Zoological Institute, zoological paper*, 12, 63–98.
- Dahlbom, G. (1835a) Conspectus Tenthredinidum, Siricidum et Oryssinorum Scandinaviae, quas Hymenopterorum familias. *Kongl. Svenska Vetenskaps Academiens Handlingar*, 1835, 1–16.
- Dahlbom, G. (1835b) *Clavis Novi Hymenopterorum Systematis adjecta Synposi Larvarum ejusdem ordinis Scandinavicarum Eruciformium*. C. F. Berling, Lundae, pp. i–v + 1–40.
- Dalla Torre, K.W.V. (1894) *Catalogus Hymenopterorum hucusque descriptorum systematicus et synonymicus*. Vol. 1: *Tenthredinidae incl. Uroceridae (Phyllophaga & Xylophaga)*. Sumptibus Guilelmi Engelmann, Lipsiae, [6 pp.] + pp. I–VIII + 1–459. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.10348>
- Damianitsch, R. (1866) Hymenopterologische Beiträge. *Verhandlungen der kaiserlich-königlichen zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien, Abhandlungen*, 16, 993–996.
- Davoudi, Z. (1987) Pear sawfly in Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 54(1–2), 45–46.
- Davoudi, Z. (1995) A study of the bioecology of plum sawfly (*Hoplocampa flava*) on the outskirts of Karadj City. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 62(4–6), Ar13–27.
- De-Stefani, T. (1883) *Miscellanea Imenotterologica. II Naturalista siciliano: giornale di scienze naturali*, 3(1), 9–13.
- De-Stefani Perez, T. (1885) *Imenotteri nuovi o poco conosciuti della Sicilia. II Naturalista siciliano: giornale di scienze naturali*, 4(8), 185–189.
- Dietrich, K. (1868) Beiträge zur Kenntnis der im Kanton Zürich einheimischen Insekten. Zwei-bis vierundzwanzigste Centurie. Hymenoptera. Fam. Tenthredonidae. *Mitteilungen der Schweizerischen Entomologischen Gesellschaft*, 2(9), 347–355.
- Dovnar-Zapolskij, D.P. (1926) O steblevyh pilil'shhikah (Cephidae) Severo-Kavkazskogo Kraja. [On stem sawflies (Cephidae) of the North Caucasus area. In Russian, new species also in German]. *Izvestija Severo-Kavkazskoj Krajevoj Stancii zaschtschity rastenij*, 1, 127–132.
- Dovnar-Zapolskij, D.P. (1930) Neue oder wenig bekannte Chalastogastren. *Russkoe Entomologicheskoe obozrenie*, 24(1–2), 86–94.
- Dovnar-Zapolskij, D.P. (1931) Cephiden Studien (Hymenoptera, Chalastogastra) (I. Beitrag). *Ezhegodnik Zoologitscheskogo Muzeja Leningrad*, 32, 37–49.
- Drapiez, P.A.J. (1819) Description de huit espèces d'insectes nouveaux. *Annales générales des sciences physiques (Bruxelles)*, 2, 197–204.
- Drapiez, P.A.J. (1820) Description de huit espèces d'insectes nouveaux. *Annales générales des sciences physiques (Bruxelles)*, 5, 117–123.
- Ebrahimi, E. (1995) Three new records of Symphyta from Iran. *Proceedings of the 12th Iranian plant protection congress*, pp. 337.
- Enslin, E. (1910) Das Tenthrediniden-Genus *Allantus* Jur. *Russkoe entomologitscheskoje obozrenije*, 10(4), 335–372.
- Enslin, E. (1912a) Über *Tenthredo* (*Allantus*) *albiventris* Mocs. und *trivittata* Ed. André, sowie über einige Namensänderungen bei *Tenthredo* und *Tenthredella*. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*, 78 Abt. A(6), 101–105.
- Enslin, E. (1912b) Die Tenthredinoidea Mitteleuropas. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, [1912](Beiheft 1), 1–98.
- Enslin, E. (1913) Die Tenthredinoidea Mitteleuropas II. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, [1913](Beiheft 2), 99–202.
- Enslin, E. (1914a) Ueber einige Tenthrediniden aus Kleinasien und Kaukasien. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*, 79 Abt. A [1913](8), 55–59.
- Enslin, E. (1914b) Ueber Tenthrediniden aus Spanien. Nebst einer Bestimmungstabelle der paläarktischen *Tomostethus*. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte*, 79 Abt. A[1913](9), 165–171.

- Enslin, E. (1914c) Die Tenthredinoidea Mitteleuropas III. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, [1914](Beiheft 3), 203–309.
- Enslin, E. (1916) Die Tenthredinoidea Mitteleuropas V. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, [1916](Beiheft 5), 413–538.
- Enslin, E. (1917) Die Tenthredinoidea Mitteleuropas VI. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, [1917](Beiheft 6), 539–662.
- Enslin, E. (1918) Die Tenthredinoidea Mitteleuropas VII. (Schluß). *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, [1917](Beiheft 7), 663–790.
- Enslin, E. (1920) Die Blattwespengattung *Tenthredo* L. (*Tenthredella* Rohwer). *Abhandlungen der Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Österreich*, 11(1), 1–96.
- Ermolenko, V.M. (1975) Rohoxvosty ta pyl"shhyky. Vypusk 3. Arhidy. Dypriionidy. Tentredynidy (selandriyiny, doleryny). (In Ukrainian). *Fauna Ukrayiny*, 10(3), 1–374.
- Esmaili, M. (1983) *Pests of fruit crops*. Sepehr, Tehran. [In Persian]
- Esmaili, M., Mirkarimi, S.A. & Azmayesh Fard, P. (1991) *Agricultural Entomology*. University of Tehran, Tehran. [In Persian]
- Eversmann, E. (1847) Fauna hymenopterologica volgo-uralensis exhibens Hymenopterorum species quas in provinciis Volgam fluvium inter et montes Uralenses situs observavit et nunc descripsit. *Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou*, 20(1), 3–68.
- Fabricius, J.C. (1775) *Systema Entomologiae sistens Insectorum classes, ordines, genera, species, adjectis synonymis, locis, descriptionibus, observationibus*. Korte, Flensburgi et Lipsiae, [30] + 832 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.36510>
- Fabricius, J.C. (1779) *Reise nach Norwegen mit Bemerkungen aus der Naturhistorie und Oekonomie*. C. E. Bohn, Hamburg, LXIV + 388 + [12] pp.
- Fabricius, J.C. (1781) *Species Insectorum exhibentes eorum differentias specificas, synonyma auctorum, loca natalia, metamorphosin adiectis observationibus, descriptionibus*, Vol. 1. Impensis Carol. Ernest. Bohnii, Hamburgi et Kilonii, pp. I–VIII + 1–552.
- Fabricius, J.C. (1787) *Mantissa Insectorum sistens eorum species nuper detectas adiectis characteribus genericis differentiis specificis emendationibus observationibus*, Vol. 1. C. G. Proft, Hafniae, pp. 1–348.
- Fabricius, J.C. (1793) *Entomologica systematica emendata et aucta. Secundum classes, ordines, genera, species adjectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus*, Vol. 2. C. G. Proft, Hafniae, pp. 104–132.
- Fabricius, J.C. (1798) *Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae*. Proft et Storch, Hafniae, 572 pp.
- Fabricius, J.C. (1804) *Systema Piezatorum secundum ordines, genera, species adiectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus*. Carolus Reichard, Brunsvigae, pp. 1–30 + 1–440.
- Fallén, C.F. (1807) Försök till uppställning och beskrifning å de i Sverige fundne Arter af Insect-Slägtet *Tenthredo* Linn. *Kongl. Vetenskaps Academiens nya Handlingar*, 28(3), 179–209.
- Fallén, C.F. (1808) Försök till uppställning och beskrifning å de i Sverige fundne Arter af Insect-Slägtet *Tenthredo* Linn. *Kongl. Vetenskaps Academiens nya Handlingar*, 29(2), 98–124.
- Fallén, C.F. (1829) *Monographia Tenthredinidum Sveciae*. Gothorum, Berling, Londini, pp. 1–48.
- Farahbakhsh, G. (1961) Checklist of important insects and other enemies of plants and agricultural products in Iran. Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Plant Protection, Tehran.
- Fischer von Waldheim, G. (1843) *Observata quaedam de Hymenopteris rossicus. Magasin de Zoologie, d'anatomie comparée et de Palaeontologie. Deuxième Serie. Troisième section. Annélides, Crustacés, Arachnides et Insectes*, 5(13), 1–4.
- Forsius, R. (1918a) Über einige paläarktische Tenthredinini. *Meddelanden af Societas pro Fauna et Flora Fennica*, 44[1917–1918], 141–153.
- Forsius, R. (1918b) Über einige von Bequaert in Nordafrika gesammelte Tenthredinoiden. *Översigt af Finska Vetenskaps Societetens Förhandlingar*, 60[1917–1918] (13), 1–11.
- Förster, A. (1850) Eine Centurie neuer Hymenopteren. Erste Dekade. *Verhandlungen des naturhistorischen Vereines der preussischen Rheinlande und Westfalens (Westphalens)*, 7, 277–288.

- Förster, A. (1854a) Neue Blattwespen. *Verhandlungen des naturhistorischen Vereines der preussischen Rheinlande und Westfalens, Neue Folge*, 1, 265–350.
- Förster, A. (1854b) Neue Blattwespen. *Verhandlungen des naturhistorischen Vereines der preussischen Rheinlande und Westfalens, Neue Folge*, 1, 421–436.
- Forster, J.R. (1771) *Novae species insectorum. Centuria I.* T. Davies & B. White, Londini, pp. i–iv + 1–100.
- Freymuth, E.K. (1870) *Pompholyx dimorpha* sp. n. Novaja bezkrylaja forma iz semejstva pililshchikob (Tenthredinidae) I ivskolko drugich novych vidov etogo semejstva. *Protocole 47me séance société d'anthropologie Moscou [Izvestija Obscestva Ljubitelej Estestvoznaniya, Antropologii i Etnografii]*, 8, 213–225.
- Gahan, A.B. (1920) Black grain stem sawfly of Europe in the United States. *Technical Bulletin, U.S. Department of Agriculture*, 834, 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.64398>
- Gasparini, R. (1891) Prilog fauni dalmatinskih pauka (Aranea et Opiliones) [Tenthredinidum species nova]. *God. Izvoješće vel. realke za god 1890/91, Spalato*, pp. 1–18 + [1, unpag.].
- Geoffroy, E.L. (1785) In: Fourcroy, A.F. de *Entomologia Parisiensis, sive catalogus Insectorum quae in agro parisiensi reperiuntur. Vol.1–2.* Paris, pp. i–viii + 1–231 + [232]–544.
- Ghadiri, V. (1993) Surveying of infestation and damage of cereal sawfly (*Cephus pygmaeus* L.) in various cultivars of wheat and barley. *Journal of the Entomological Society of Iran*, 12–13, 4–5.
- Ghadiri, V. (1994a) Studies on the biological features of cereal sawfly (*Cephus pygmaeus* L.) in Karadj district. *Journal of the Entomological Society of Iran*, 14 (7–8), 27–33.
- Ghadiri, V. (1994b) The effect of harvesting date in reduction of cereal sawfly population (*Cephus pygmaeus* L.). *Seed and Plant*, 10 (3–4), 7, Ar 44–47.
- Ghadiri, V. (2000) Research of fenitrothion effect (used on sunn pest) on reduction of population density of cereal sawfly (*Cephus pygmaeus* L.). *Journal of Agricultural Sciences - Islamic Azad University*, 6 (3), 57–63.
- Ghadiri, V. & Irani, P. (1999) The effects of cereal stem sawfly damages on qualitative characters and baking value of some wheat cultivars. *Seed and Plant*, 14 (4), 39–45.
- Ghadiri, V. & Safai, N. (2001) Effect of plant density on infestation of wheat by cereal stem sawfly (*Cephus pygmaeus* L.). *Seed and Plant*, 17 (3), 286–293.
- Ghigi, A. (1905) Catalogo dei Tenthredinidi del Museo zoologico di Napoli con osservazioni critiche e sinonimiche. *Annuario del Museo Zoologico della R. Università di Napoli*, N. S, 1[1904](21), 1–28.
- Gimmerthal, B.A. (1836) Beschreibung einiger neuen in Liefland aufgefundenen Insecten. *Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou*, 9, 429–449.
- Giraud, J. (1863) Mémoire sur les Insectes qui vivent sur le Roseau commun, *Phragmites communis* Trin. (*Arundo phragmites* L.) et plus spécialement sur ceux de l'ordre des Hyménoptères. *Verhandlungen der kaiserlich-königlichen zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien, Abhandlungen*, 13, 1251–1288.
- Gmelin, J.F. (1790) *Caroli a Linné Systema Naturae. 13. ed., Vol. 1(5).* Beer, Leipzig, pp. 2225–3020.
- Gradl, H. (1878) Zu Macrophyta. Varietäten und Variationen. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 4, 239–240.
- Gravenhorst, J.L.C. (1807) *Vergleichende Uebersicht des Linneischen und einiger neuern zoologischen Systeme [. . .] nebst dem eingeschalteten Verzeichnisse der zoologischen Sammlung des Verfassers und den Beschreibungen neuer Thierarten, die in derselben vorhanden sind.* Bey Heinrich Dieterich, Göttingen, XX + 476 pp.
- Gregor, F. (1927) Prispěvek pro poznání pilatek podk. rúsi. *Časopis Československé Společnosti entomologické*, 24(1–2), 29–38.
- Gregor, F. & Baťa, L. (1942) Prodrómus našeho blanokřídleho hmyzu. Prodrómus Hymenopterorum patriae nostrae. Pars V.[recte VI] Podřád Symphyta (Chalastogastera, Tenthredinoidea.) Fam. Tenthredinidae: Subfam. Dolerinae, Selandriinae, Hoplocampinae, Blennocampinae, Nematinae. *Sborník Entomologického Oddělení při zoologických sbírkách Zemského Musea v Praze*, 20(250), 259–344.

- Gribodo, G. (1881) Escursione in Calabria (1877–78). *Bulletino della Società Entomologica Italiana*, 13, 43–74.
- Guérin-Méneville, F.É. (1844) Neuvième Ordre. – Hyménoptères. In: Guérin-Méneville, F.É. (1829–1844): *Iconographie du Règne animal de G. Cuvier, ou représentation d'après nature, de l'une des espèces les plus remarquables et souvent non encore figurées, de chaque genre d'animaux, avec un texte descriptif mis au courant de la science. Ouvrage pouvant servir d'atlas a tous les traités de zoologie*, Vol. 7.J.J. Ballière, Paris, pp. 398–466.
- Guiglia, D. (1956) Una nuova species di *Pseudoryssus* dell'Italia Settentrionale. *Bolletino della Società Entomologica Italiana*, 86, 24–25.
- Gussakovskij, V.V. (1935) Insectes Hyménoptères, Chalastrogastra 1. *Fauna SSSR*, 2(1), 1–453.
- Haris, A. (1996) New East-Palaeartic *Dolerus* species (Hymenoptera, Symphyta, Tenthredinidae). *Acta Zoologica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae*, 42(3), 187–194.
- Harris, T.W. (1835) VIII. Insects. In: Hitchcock, E., *Report on the geology, mineralogy, botany, and zoology of Massachusetts. Made and published by order of the government of that state: in four parts: part I. Economical geology. Part II. Topographical geology. part III. Scientific geology. part IV. Catalogues of animals and plants. With a descriptive list of the specimens of rocks and minerals collected for the government. Illustrated by numerous wood cuts and an atlas of plates. Second edition, corrected and enlarged*. Press of J.S. and C. Adams, Amherst, pp. 553–602.
- Harris, T.W. (1845) [There is but one more leaf-eating insect. Raspberry Worm]. In: Darling, N. An address upon injurious Insects; delivered before the New Haven Horticultural Society, and the New Haven County Agricultural Society; at their annual Fair, October 1st, 1845. *Transactions of the New Haven Horticultural Society and the New Haven County Agricultural Society 1845*, pp. 13–14.
- Hartig, T. (1837) *Die Aderflügler Deutschlands mit besonderer Berücksichtigung ihres Larvenzustandes und ihres Wirkens in Wäldern und Gärten für Entomologen, Wald- und Gartenbesitzer. Die Familien der Blattwespen und Holzwespen nebst einer allgemeinen Einleitung zur Naturgeschichte der Hymenopteren. Erster Band*. Haude und Spener, Berlin, pp. i–xiv + 1–416.
- Hartig, T. (1840) Hymenopterologische Mittheilungen vom Forstrathe Dr. Th. Hartwig. [sic!] *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 1(2), 19–28.
- Hellén, W. (1948) Mitteilungen über einige Tenthredinoiden aus Ostfennoskandien. *Notulae Entomologicae*, 28, 40–46.
- Heller, C. & Dalla Torre, C.v. (1883) Über die Verbreitung der Thierwelt im Tiroler Hochgebirge. *Sitzungsberichte der kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften. Mathematisch-naturwissenschaftliche Classe*, 86(1–5), 8–53.
- Hering, M. (1935) Vorläufige Beschreibung von 3 neuen Phytomyza- und 2 neuen Tenthrediniden-Arten. In: Hering, M. *Die Blattminen Mittel- und Nord-Europas einschließlich Englands. Bestimmungstabellen aller von Insektenlarven der verschiedenen Ordnungen erzeugten Minen*, Vol. 1. Gustav Feller Verlag, Neubrandenburg, pp. xi–xii.
- Herrich-Schäffer, G.A.W. (1840) *Nomenclator entomologicus. Verzeichniss der europäischen Insecten, zur Erleichterung des Tauschverkehrs mit Preisen versehen*. Regensburg. Coleoptera, Orthoptera, Dermaptera, Hymenoptera. F. Pustet, Regensburg, pp. VIII + 1–244.
- Jakowlew, A. (1888) Quelques nouvelles espèces des mouches à scie de l'Empire Russe. *Trudy Russkogo Entomologiceskogo Obscestva v S. Peterburge*, 22, 368–375.
- Jakowlew, A. (1891) Diagnoses Tenthredinidarum novarum ex Rossia Europaea, Sibiria, Asia Media et confinum. *Trudy Russkogo Entomologiceskogo Obscestva v S. Peterburge*, 26[1892], 1–62.
- Jurine, L. (1807) *Nouvelle Méthode de classer les Hyménoptères et les Diptères*, Vol. 4(II). Genève & Paris, pp. 1–319 + plates 1–7.
- Karimpour, Y. (2007a) Biology of the *Rumex* leaf defoliator sawfly *Kokujewia ectrapela* Konow (Hymenoptera: Argidae) in Urmia region. *Proceedings of the XIIth International Symposium on Biological Control of Weeds*, p. 250.
- Karimpour, Y. (2007b) Host-Specificity and potential of *Kokujewia ectrapela* Konow

- (Hymenoptera: Argidae) for the control of *Rumex* spp. Proceedings of the XIIth International Symposium on Biological Control of Weeds, p. 357.
- Karimpour, Y. (2015) Biology, host specificity and feeding potential of the Dock's leaf defoliator sawfly, *Kokujewia ectrapela* Konow (Hymenoptera: Argidae), a biocontrol agent of *Rumex* spp. (Polygonaceae). *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 35(1), 1–10.
- Karimpour, Y. & Razmi, M. (2010) First report of *Cryptus inquisitor* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 29 (2), 37–39.
- Kawall, J.H. (1864) Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Hymenopteren Fauna Russlands. *Bulletin de la Société des Naturalistes de Moscou, Section biologique, Nouvelle Série*, 37, 293–303.
- Khayrandish, M., Talebi, A.A., Blank, S.M. & Fathipour, Y. (2012) Study of common sawflies of the genus *Ametastegia* (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae) in north of Iran with two new species records. Proceedings of the 20th Iranian plant protection congress, pp. 161.
- Khayrandish, M., Talebi, A.A., Blank, S.M. & Fathipour, Y. (2015) Study on the genus *Ametastegia* Costa (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae) in northern Iran with the description of a new species. *Journal of Insects Biodiversity and Systematics*, 1 (1), 17–32.
- Khayrandish, M., Talebi, A.A., Fathipour, Y. & Blank, S.M. The sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) of northern Iran, with description of a new species. *Zootaxa*, (in press).
- Khosravi, R. Jalai Sendi, J., Ebrahimi, E. & Blank, S.M. (2014) First record of *Cladius (Priophorus) rufipes* Serville, 1823 (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 33(4), 73–75.
- Kirby, W.F. (1881) A List of the Hymenoptera of New Zealand. *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London for the Year*, 1881(1), 35–50.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2311.1881.tb01531.x>
- Kirby, W.F. (1882) *List of Hymenoptera with Descriptions and Figures of the Typical Specimens in the British Museum. 1. Tenthredinidae and Siricidae Vol. 1.* By order of the Trustees, London, pp. 1–450.
- Kirby, W.F. (1886) A synopsis of the genera of the Chalcididae, subfamily Eucharinae, with descriptions of several new genera and species of Chalcididae and Tenthredinidae. *The Journal of the Linnean Society*, 20, 28–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-3642.1886.tb01433.x>
- Klima, A. (1937) Cephidae. — Syntexidae. pp. 1–53. In: Hedicke, H. (Ed.), *Hymenopterorum Catalogus*. Vol. 2. W. Junk, 's-Gravenhage, pp. 1–53.
- Klug, F. (1814) Die Blattwespen nach ihren Gattungen und Arten zusammengestellt. *Der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin Magazin für die neuesten Entdeckungen in der gesamten Naturkunde*, 6[1812] (4), 276–310.
- Klug, F. (1815) Die Blattwespen nach ihren Gattungen und Arten zusammengestellt. *Der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin Magazin für die neuesten Entdeckungen in der gesamten Naturkunde*, 7[1813](2), 120–131.
- Klug, F. (1816) Die Blattwespen nach ihren Gattungen und Arten zusammengestellt. *Der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin Magazin für die neuesten Entdeckungen in der gesamten Naturkunde*, 8[1814](1), 42–84.
- Klug, F. (1817a) Die Blattwespen nach ihren Gattungen und Arten zusammengestellt. *Der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin Magazin für die neuesten Entdeckungen in der gesamten Naturkunde*, 8[1814](2), 110–144.
- Klug, F. (1817b) Die Blattwespen nach ihren Gattungen und Arten zusammengestellt. *Der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin Magazin für die neuesten Entdeckungen in der gesamten Naturkunde*, 8[1814](3), 179–219.
- Klug, F. (1818) Die Blattwespen nach ihren Gattungen und Arten zusammengestellt. *Der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin Magazin für die neuesten Entdeckungen in der gesamten Naturkunde*, 8[1814](4), 273–307.
- Klug, F. (1820) Versuch einer Darstellung der Familien und Arten der Blattwespengattung

- Cimbex* Fabr. *Verhandlungen der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin*, 1[1819–1829](2), 71–98.
- Klug, F. (1824) Entomologische Monographien. Berlin, G. Reimer, XIV + 242 pp.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.3346>
- Klug, F. (1834) Uebersicht der Tenthredineten der Sammlung. *Jahrbücher der Insectenkunde mit besonderer Rücksicht auf die Sammlung des Königl. Museum in Berlin herausgegeben*, 1, 223–253.
- Koch, F. (1988) Die Gattung *Sterictiphora* Billberg (Insecta: Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Argidae). *Entomologische Abhandlungen*, 52(2), 29–61.
- Konow, F.W. (1884) Bemerkungen über Blattwespen. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 28 (2), 305–354.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.13857>
- Konow, F.W. (1885a) Ueber die Blattwespen Gattungen *Strongylogaster* Dahlb. und *Selandria* Klg. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 4, 19–26.
- Konow, F.W. (1885b) Ueber Blattwespen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 4(10), 295–301.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.20138>
- Konow, F.W. (1885c) Bemerkungen über einige Blattwespengattungen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 4(4), 117–124.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.20108>
- Konow, F.W. (1886a) Bemerkungen über Blattwespen. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 30 (1), 73–82.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mmnd.48018860106>
- Konow, F.W. (1886b) Sieben neue Allantus-Arten. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 5, 17–21.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.20548>
- Konow, F.W. (1886c) Ueber mehrere neue und einige schon bekannte Blattwespen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 5, 37–41.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.20551>
- Konow, F.W. (1887a) Neue griechische und einige andere Blattwespen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 6(1), 19–28.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.17725>
- Konow, F.W. (1887b) Nachtrag zu den Blenno-campiden. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 6 (10), 273–283.
- Konow, F.W. (1888a) Die Blattwespengattung *Allantus* Jur. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 32, 209–220.
- Konow, F.W. (1888b) Zwei neue Blattwespenarten. *Sitzungsberichte der Preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin*, 1888, 187–193.
- Konow, F.W. (1890a) Tableaux analytique et systematique du genre *Tenthredopsis* Costa. *Revue d'Entomologie*, 9, 63–80.
- Konow, F.W. (1890b) Neue paläarktische Blattwespen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 9(1), 8–13.
- Konow, F.W. (1891) Neue Blattwespen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 10(2), 41–48.
- Konow, F.W. (1892) Bemerkungen und Nachträge zum Catalogus Tenthredinidarum Europae. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 1891(2), 209–220.
- Konow, F.W. (1894a) Neue Tenthrediniden. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 13, 129–139.
- Konow, F.W. (1894b) Neue europäische Blattwespen, nebst Bemerkungen über einige bisher verkannte Arten. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 13, 84–96.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.13219>
- Konow, F.W. (1895) Neue paläarktische Blattwespen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 14(3), 71–78.
- Konow, F.W. (1896a) Neue und einige bisher verkannte Arten aus der Familie der Tenthrediniden. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 22(20), 308–319.
- Konow, F.W. (1896b) Verschiedenes aus der Hymenopteren-Gruppe der Tenthrediniden. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 15, 41–59.
- Konow, F.W. (1896c) Ueber Blattwespen, Tribus Cephini (Tenthredinarum Tribus). *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 15(4–5), 150–179.
- Konow, F.W. (1897a) Systematische und kritische Bearbeitung der Blattwespentribus Lydini. *Annalen des K. K. Naturhistorischen Hofmuseums*, 12, 231–255.
- Konow, F.W. (1897b) Systematische und kritische Bearbeitung der Blattwespen-

- Tribus Lydini. *Annalen des K. K. Naturhistorischen Hofmuseums*, 12(1), 1–32.
- Konow, F.W. (1897c) Zwei neue Siriciden und einige paläarktische Tenthrediniden. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 23(24), 372–376.
- Konow, F.W. (1898a) Ueber einige neue Chalastogastra Arten. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 24(21), 327–330.
- Konow, F.W. (1898b) Neue Arten aus den Blattwespen-Gattungen *Allantus* Jur. und *Tenthredopsis* Costa. Verhandlungen der kaiserl.-königl. Zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien, 48, 324–334.
- Konow, F.W. (1898c) Neue Tenthrediniden. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 17(7–8), 228–238.
- Konow, F.W. (1899a) Chalastogastrorum novae species et varietates, quas D. Escalera ex Asia minore reportavit. *Actas de la Sociedad Española de Historia Natural*, 28(7), 203–207.
- Konow, F.W. (1899b) Neue südamerikanische Tenthredinidae. *Anales del Museo Nacional de Buenos Aires*, 2. Ser., 3=6, 397–417.
- Konow, F.W. (1899c) Neue Tenthredinidae. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 25(23), 359–366.
- Konow, F.W. (1902a) Die Nematiden-Gattung *Pristiphora* Latr. (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae) soweit dieselbe bisher aus der palaearktischen Zone bekannt ist. *Ezhegodnik" Zoologicheskago Muzeja Imperatorskoj Akademii Nauk"*, 7, 161–187.
- Konow, F.W. (1902b) Neue Blattwespen. (Hym). *Zeitschrift für systematische Hymenopterologie und Dipterologie*, 2(6), 384–390.
- Konow, F.W. (1904a) Ein neuer *Entodecta* Knw. (Hym.). *Zeitschrift für systematische Hymenopterologie und Dipterologie*, 4(1), 4–5.
- Konow, F.W. (1904b) Neue paläarktische Chalastogastra. (Hym.) (Fortsetzung). *Zeitschrift für systematische Hymenopterologie und Dipterologie*, 4(5), 260–270.
- Konow, F.W. (1905a) Hymenoptera. Fam. Tenthredinidae. Fasc. 29. In: Wytsman, P. (Ed.), *Genera Insectorum*, Brüssel, Bruxelles, pp. 1–176.
- Konow, F.W. (1905b) Neue exotische Tenthrediniden. (Hym.). *Zeitschrift für systematische Hymenopterologie und Dipterologie*, 5(3), 157–166.
- Konow, F.W. (1906) Einige neue paläarktische und orientalische Tenthrediniden. *Zeitschrift für systematische Hymenopterologie und Dipterologie*, 6 (4), 254–256.
- Konow, F.W. (1907) Neue Blattwespen (Hym.). *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 489–497.
- Korlević, A. (1890) Prilozi fauni hrvatskih opnokrilaca. [Contributions to the Hymenoptera of the Croatian fauna.] (In Croatian). *Glasnik Hrvatskoga Naravoslovnoga Društva, Zagreb*, 5, 189–265.
- Kriechbaumer, J. (1891) Zwei neue Macrophyarten. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 17(12), 188–191.
- Kuznetzov-Ugamskij, N.N. (1927) Neue Blattwespen aus Mittel-Asien. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*, 71(9–10), 273–278.
- Lacourt, J. (1987) Note sur *Pristiphora pallidiventris* (Fallén) (= *Pristiphora denudata* Konow) avec description de deux nouvelles sous-espèces (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae). *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie. Nouvelle Série*, 4(3), 259–264.
- Lacourt, J. (1988) Une nouvelle espèce d'*Empria* Lepelletier d'Espagne (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae). *L'Entomologiste. Revue d'Amateurs*, 44(6), 309–312.
- Lacourt, J. (1998) Désignation de lectotypes pour des *Elinora* Benson des collections Kriechbaumer et Enslin [Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae]. *Revue française d'Entomologie*, (N. S.) 20(1–2), 24–26.
- Lacourt, J. (1999) Répertoire des Tenthredinidae ouest-paléarctiques (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Mémoires de la SEF*, 3, 1–432.
- Leach, W.E. (1817) *The Zoological Miscellany. Being Descriptions of New or Interesting Animals Vol.3*. R. and A. Taylor, Shoe-Lane, London, pp. 1–151.
- Lepelletier, A.L.M. (1823) *Monographia Tenthredinetarum synonymia extricata*. Apud Auctorem [etc.], Parisiis, pp. 1–176. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.10485>
- Lepelletier, A.L.M. (=Le Peletier de Saint-Fargeau, A.) (1834) Description de trois nouvelles espèces du G. *Cimbex*. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France*, 2, 454–455.
- Lindqvist, E. (1949) Neue nordische Blattwespen. *Notulae Entomologicae*, 28[1948], 65–86.

- Lindqvist, E. (1964) Neue Blattwespen (Hym., Tenthredinidae). *Notulae Entomologicae*, 44, 121–132.
- Linnaeus, C. (1758) *Systema Naturae, per regna tria naturae secundum classes, ordines, genera, species cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Editio Decima Reformata. (10th ed.) Vol. 1.* Laurentius Salvius, Holmiae, pp. 1–824.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.542>
- Linnaeus, C. (1760) *Fauna Svecica sistens animalia Sveciae regni: Mammalia, Aves, Amphibia, Pisces, Insecta, Vermes. Distributa per classes & ordines, genera & species, cum differentiis specierum, synonymis auctorum, nominibus incolarum, locis natalium, descriptionibus insectorum. Editio altera, auctior.* Laurentius Salvius, Stockholmiae ["1761"], 578 pp.
- Linnaeus, C. (1767) *Systema naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Editio Duodecima Reformata (12ed.) Tom. I. Pars II.* Laur. Salvii, Holmiae, pp. 533–1328 + 34 pp. + 2 pp.
- Liston, A.D. (1995) Compendium of European Sawflies. List of species, modern nomenclature, distribution, food plants, identification literature. Chalastos Forestry, Gottfrieding.
- Liston, A.D. (2004) The hostplant and larva of *Allantus didymus* (Klug, 1818) (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 114(2), 50–51.
- Liston, A.D. & Späth, J. (2005) New data on the sawfly fauna of Corsica with the description of a new species *Pontania cyrnea* sp. nov. (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Nachrichtenblatt der Bayerischen Entomologen*, 54(1–2), 2–7.
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1893) Washington Tenthredinidae and Uroceridae. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 25(10), 237–244.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent25237-10>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1908) Blennocampinae – descriptions of new genera and species – synonymical notes. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 40 (9), 289–297.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent38305-9>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1909) A new genus and some new species of Tenthredinidae. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 41(10), 345–362.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent41345-10>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1911) New species of *Empria*. I. – Eastern Species. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 43(9), 305–311.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent43305-9>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1914) New genera and species of sawflies. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 46 (10), 363–367.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent46363-10>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1916) Tenthredinoidea. In: Viereck, H.L. (Ed.), Guide to the Insects of Connecticut. Part III. The Hymenoptera or Wasp-Like Insects of Connecticut. *Bulletin 22 / State Geological and Natural History Survey of Connecticut*, pp. 25–175.
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1920) New saw-flies from Maine and New York (Hymenoptera). *The Canadian Entomologist*, 52(10), 233–236.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent52233-10>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1921a) New species of Nematinae – (Hymenoptera). *Journal of the New York Entomological Society*, 29(1), 27–35.
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1921b) New species of Emphytinae and Selandriinae – Hymenoptera. *Psyche*, 28(2), 31–35.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/1921/26413>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1923a) New species of Tenthredinidae from the East and Middle West. *Bulletin of the Brooklyn Entomological Society*, 18, 53–56.
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1923b) Sawflies from Alberta (Tenthredinidae). *The Canadian Entomologist*, 55(7), 158–162.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent55158-7>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1923c) Saw-flies of the Katmai Expedition to Alaska. *Journal of the New York Entomological Society*, 31(4), 163–171.
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1923d) New saw-flies, Hymenoptera, from Oregon. *Psyche*, 30(2), 77–81.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/1923/90450>
- MacGillivray, A.D. (1923e) A Century of Tenthredinoidea. *University of Illinois Bulletin*, 20(50), 1–38.
- Magretti, P. (1886) Varietà e specie nuove di Imenotteri Terebranti Tenthredinidei. *Bulletino della Società Entomologica Italiana*, 18, 24–29.
- Magretti, P. (1890) Imenotteri di Siria raccolti dall'avv.to Augusto Medana, R. Console d

- Italia a tripoli si Siria, con descizione di alcune specie nuove. *Annali del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Genova, Série 2*, 9 (29), 522-528.
- Malaise, R. (1931) Blattwespen aus Wladiwostok und anderen Teilen Ostasiens. *Entomologisk Tidskrift*, 52(2), 97-159.
- Mallach, N. (1931) Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Insektenfauna Nordpersiens. *Entomologisches Nachrichtenblatt*, 5, 81-82.
- Marlatt, C.L. (1896) Revision of the Nematinae of North America, a subfamily of leaf-feeding Hymenoptera of the family Tenthredinidae. *Technical Series, United States Department of Agriculture, Division of Entomology*, 3, 1-135.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.40958>
- Matsumura, S. (1911) Erster Beitrag zur Insektenfauna Sachalins. *The journal of the College of Agriculture, Tohoku Imperial University*, 4, 1-145.
- Matsumura, S. (1912) *Thousand insects of Japan. Supplement IV*. Keiseisha, Tokyo, 1-247.
- Middlekauff, W.W. (1969) The cephid stem borers of California (Hymenoptera: Cephidae). *Bulletin of the California Insect Survey*, 11, 1-19.
- Mocsáry, A. (1877) Hymenoptera nova in collectione Musei nationalis Hungarici. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 1 (2), 87-91.
- Mocsáry, A. (1879) Hymenoptera nova e fauna Hungarica. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 3 (2-3), 115-141.
- Mocsáry, A. (1880) Hymenoptera nova e variis orbis terrarum partibus. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 4 (4), 267-275.
- Mocsáry, A. (1881) Hymenoptera nova e variis orbis terrarum partibus. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 5(1), 29-37.
- Mocsáry, A. (1883) Hymenoptera nova europaea et exotica. *Értekezések a természettudományok köréből*, 13(11), 1-72.
- Mocsáry, A. (1886a) Species aliquot Tenthredini-darum novae, ab Alexandro Mocsáry descriptae. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 12 (1), 2-3.
- Mocsáry, A. (1886b) A magyarországi fa-rontó darázsok. IV. *Rovartani Lapok*, 3, 98-106.
- Mocsáry, A. (1891) Tenthredinidae et Siricidae novae. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 14(3-4), 155-159.
- Mocsáry, A. (1909) Chalastogastra nova in collectione Musei nationalis Hungarici. *Annales historico-naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 7, 1-39.
- Mocsáry, A. (1910) Über *Orussus unicolor* Latr. und eine nah verwandte neue Art aus Kroatien. *Annales historico-naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 8, 160-162.
- Modarres Awal, M. (1997) List of agricultural pests and their natural enemies in Iran. Ferdowsi University Press, Mashad.
- Muche, W.H. (1962) Die Tenthredinidae (Hym.) meiner Anatolienausbeute II. *Reichenbachia*, 1(3), 17-20.
- Muche, W.H. (1971) Die entomologisch fast unbekannte Umgebung von Ordshonikidse (Kaukasus). *Entomologische Nachrichten (Dresden)*, 15 (6), 53-55.
- Muche, W.H. (1972) Beitrag zur Kenntnis der *Netocia hungarica* Herbst und kaukasischer Blattwespen am Maschuk. *Entomologische Nachrichten (Dresden)*, 16 (6), 66-68.
- Muche, W.H. (1973) 4. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Symphyten des Kaukasus (Hymenoptera). *Faunistische Abhandlungen Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde Dresden*, 4 (10), 77-97.
- Muche, W.H. (1975) Eine neue Unterart von *Aglaostigma langei* (Konow) aus dem Kaukasus (Hymenoptera Symphyta). *Faunistische Abhandlungen Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde Dresden*, 5(9), 239-240.
- Muche, W.H. (1977) Die Argidae von Europa, Vorderasien und Nordafrika (mit Ausnahme der Gattung *Aprosthemata*) (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Entomologische Abhandlungen*, 41, Supplement: 23-59.
- Newman, E. (1837) Notes on Tenthredinina. *The Entomological Magazine, London*, 4[1836-1837](3), 258-263.
- Niezabitowski, E.L. (1899) Materiały do fauny rośliniarek (Phytophaga) Galicyi. *Sprawozdán Komisji fizyograficznej Akademii Umiejętności w Krakowie*, 34, 3-17.
- Noblecourt, T. (2004) *Liste Systématique des Hyménoptères Symphytes de France. Rapport d'étude dans le cadre du DEA de Biologie, Université de Mons-Hainaut, Laboratoire de*

- zoologie. Office National des Forêts, Cellule d'études entomologiques, Quillan, 80 pp.
- Norton, E. (1860) On the Hymenoptera of the Genus *Allantus* in the United States. *Boston Journal of Natural History*, 7[1859-1863](2), 236-260.
- Norton, E. (1861) Notice of the genus *Selandria*. *Proceedings of the Boston Society of Natural History*, 8, 219-224.
- Norton, E. (1862) Catalogue of American species of *Tenthredo*, as arranged by Hartig. *Proceedings of the Boston Society of Natural History*, 9[1862-1863], 116-122.
- Norton, E. (1864) Notes on *Tenthredinidae*, with descriptions of new species in the collection of the Entomological Society. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Philadelphia*, 3, 5-16.
- Norton, E. (1867a) Catalogue of the described *Tenthredinidae* and *Uroceridae* of North America. *Transactions of the American Entomological Society*, 1(2), 193-224. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25076177>
- Norton, E. (1867b) Catalogue of the described *Tenthredinidae* and *Uroceridae* of North America. *Transactions of the American Entomological Society*, 1(3), 225-280.
- Palma, G. (1861) Su talune specie d'Imenotteri Tentredinidei della Fauna Napolitana. *Annali dell'Accademia degli Aspiranti Naturalisti, Série 2, 1*, 93-98.
- Panzer, G.W.F. (1799) *Faunae Insectorum Germanicae initia oder Deutschlands Insecten*. Felssecker, Nürnberg, 6(61-72), each 1-24.
- Panzer, G.W.F. (1801) *Faunae Insectorum Germanicae initia oder Deutschlands Insecten*. Felssecker, Nürnberg, 7 [1799-1801](81-83), each 1-24.
- Panzer, G.W.F. (1803) *Faunae Insectorum Germanicae initia oder Deutschlands Insecten*. Felssecker, Nürnberg, 8[1801-1804] (86-94), 1-24.
- Panzer, G.W.F. (1804) *D. Jacobi Christiani Schaefferi Iconum Insectorum circa Ratisbonam indigenorum. Enumeratio Systematica*. [second title:] *D. G.W.F. Panzeri Enumerationis Systematicae D. Jac. Christiani Schaefferi Iconum Insectorum Ratisbonensium. Dr. G.W.F. Panzers systematische Nomenklatur über Dr. Jac. Christian Schäffers Abbildungen regensburgischer Insekten. Pars Tertia*. J. Jacob Palm, Erlangen, pp. i-xvi, i-viii, 1-260.
- Panzer, G.W.F. (1806) *Kritische Revision der Insektenfauna Deutschlands nach dem System bearbeitet. II. Bändchen, I.-C. Heft*. [second title:] *Entomologischer Versuch die Jürineschen Gattungen der Linnéschen Hymenoptern nach dem Fabriziusschen System zu prüfen: im Bezug auf die in der deutschen Insektenfauna bekannt gemachten Gattungen und Arten dieser Klasse*. Felssecker, Nürnberg, [14] + 271 pp.
- Pasteels, J. (1946) Notules sur les Hyménoptères Symphytes (2me Série). *Bulletin & Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique*, 82, 245-248.
- Perty, J.A.M. (1830) *Delectus animalium articulatorum, quae in itinere per Brasiliam annis MDCCCXVII -MDCCCXX jussu et auspiciis Maximiliani Josephi I. Bavariae regis augustissimi peracto collegerunt Dr. J. B. de Spix . . . et Dr. C. F. Ph. de Martius. digessit, descripsit, pingenda curavit Dr. Maximilianus Perty, Praefatus est et edidit Carol. Frideri. Philip. de Martius. Accedit Dissertatio de insectorum in America meridionali habitantium vitiae genere, moribus et distributione geographica. Monachii, impensis Editoris. 1830-1834. (3 Fasc.). Monachii, prostat apud Editorem, Lipsiae apud Frid. Fleischer in Comm. Impensis Editoris, Monachii, pp. [1-2] + I-III + 1-44 + 1-224.*
- Pic, M. (1916) Hyménoptères nouveaux d'Orient et de Nord de d'Afrique. *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 32(378), 23-24.
- Pic, M. (1917) Sur le genre "*Arge*" Schr. (*Hylotoma* Latr.). *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 33 (383), 18-19.
- Pic, M. (1918) Descriptions diverses de *Tenthredinides* et notes. *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 34(388), 1-4.
- Pic, M. (1920) Nouveaux Hyménoptères paléarctiques. *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 36(400), 13-15.
- Pic, M. (1925) Hyménoptères nouveaux (Suite.). *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 31(422), 14-15.
- Pic, M. (1926) Hyménoptères nouveaux. II. *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 32(425), 11-12.
- Pic, M. (1928) Hyménoptères nouveaux. *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 34(432), 6-7.

- Pic, M. (1929) Tenthredinides et Ichneumoniens (Hym.). *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 45(435), 3.
- Pic, M. (1948a) Nouveautés et Notes Hyménoptérologiques. *Diversités entomologiques*, 3, 1-11.
- Pic, M. (1948b) Tenthredinoides en partie nouveaux (Hymén). *L'Échange. Revue Linnéenne*, 64(512), 5-6.
- Poda, N. (1761) *Insecta Musei Graecensis, quae in ordines, genera et species juxta Systema Naturae Caroli Linnaei digessit Nicolaus Poda, e societate Jesu etc.* Typis Haeredum Widmanstadii, Graecii 8 + 127 + 20 pp.
- Provancher, L. (1878) Les Insectes. Hyménoptères. 1. Fam. des Tenthredinides Tenthredinidae. *Le Naturaliste Canadien*, 10, 65-73.
- Provancher, L. (1885) [Symphyta.] In: *Additions et Corrections au volume II de la faune entomologique de Canada*. C. Daeveau, Québec, [1885-1889], 5-16.
- Puls, J. (1870) Note sur les hyménoptères rapportés des provinces occidentales de la Transcaucasie par M. Théophile Deyrolle. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique*, 13, 147-152.
- Quinlan, J. & Gauld, I.D. (1981) Hymenoptera (Symphyta), (except Tenthredinidae). In Royal Entomological Society of London, *Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects*. 6(2a), 1-67.
- Radjabi, Gh. (2002) Pests rosaceous fruit trees in Iran. Ministry of Agriculture Jihad, Agricultural Research, Education and Extension Organization, Agriculture Education Publisher.
- Retzius, A.J. (1783) *Caroli De Geer (. . .) Genera et species insectorum e generosissimi auctoris scriptis extraxit, digessit, latine quoad partem reddidit, et terminologiam insectorum Linneanam addidit.* Siegfried Lebrecht Crusium, Lipsiae, pp. i-vi, 7-220, 1-32.
- Rohwer, S.A. (1909) Notes on Tenthredinoidea, with descriptions of new species. Paper II (Species from Nebraska). *The Canadian Entomologist*, 41(1), 9-21.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent419-1>
- Rohwer, S.A. (1910a) Notes on Tenthredinoidea, with descriptions of new species. Paper XII. — (Genus *Hoplocampa* L.). *The Canadian Entomologist*, 42(7), 242-244.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent42242-7>
- Rohwer, S.A. (1910b) On a collection of Tenthredinoidea from Eastern Canada. *Proceedings of the United States National Museum*, 38[1911](1739), 197-209.
<https://doi.org/10.5479/si.00963801.1739.197>
- Rohwer, S.A. (1913) A synopsis of the Nearctic species of sawflies of the genus *Xyela*, with descriptions of other new species of sawflies. *Proceedings of the United States National Museum*, 45, 265-281.
<https://doi.org/10.5479/si.00963801.45-1981.265>
- Rohwer, S.A. (1915) Descriptions of new species of Hymenoptera. *Proceedings of the United States National Museum*, 49[1916](2105), 205-249.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5479/si.00963801.2105.205>
- Rossi, P. (1790) *Fauna Etrusca sistens Insecta, quae in provinciis Florentina et Pisana praesertim collegit Petrus Rossius In regio Pisano Athenaeo.* Typis Thomae Masi & Sociorum, Liburni, XXII + 272 + 348 pp.
- Rossi, P. (1794) *Mantissa Insectorum exhibens species nuper in Etruria collectas a Petro Rossio adiectis faunae Etruscae illustrationibus, ac emendationibus.* Vol 2. Ex Typographia Prosperi, Pisis, pp. 5-154.
- Rudow, F. (1871) Die Tenthrediniden des Unterharzes, nebst einigen neuen Arten anderer Gegenden. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 32, 381-395.
- Rudow, F. (1872) Zwei neue Blattwespen. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 33, 217-218.
- Saarinén, A. (1945) *Pontania vesicator* Bremi ab. *borealis* n. ab., eine neue Tenthredinidenaberration (Hym.) aus Finnland. *Annales Entomologici Fennici*, 11(3), 194-195.
- Sahragard, A. & Heydari, R. (2001) Biology and Spatial Distribution of Rose Sawfly, *Arge rosae* (Hymenoptera: Argidae) in Guilan. *Journal of the Entomological Society of Iran*, 21(2), 25-37.
- Saini, M.S. & Bharti, H. (2000) Review of genus *Metallopeus* Malaise (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Tenthredinidae) from India with an addition of two new species. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India*, 98(1), 149-155.

- Schaposchnikow, N. (1885) *Strongylogaster caucasicus* n. sp. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 11(12), 181–182.
- Schedl, W. (1987) Die Pflanzenwespen (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) des Landesmuseums Joanneum in Graz. Teil 6: Tenthredinoidea: Familie Tenthredinidae, Unterfamilie Tenthredininae. *Mitteilungen der Abteilung für Zoologie am Landesmuseum Joanneum*, 40, 1–23.
- Schlechtendal, D.H.R.von (1878) Eine neue Deutsche Siricide *Macrocephus* (n.g.) *ulmariae* n.sp. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 4, 153–154.
- Schlechtendal, D.H.R.von (1880) Ist *Phyllaeus Giraudi* Perris = *Macrocephus ulmariae* m.? *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 6(17), 189–190.
- Schrank, F.von P. (1776) *Beyträge zur Naturgeschichte*. Gebr. Veith, Augsburg, [6] + 137 + [3] pp.
- Schrank, F.von P. (1781) *Enumeratio Insectorum Austriae indigenorum*. E. Klett et Franck, Augustae Vindelicorum, Tbl. + [22] + 1–548 + [2] pp.
- Schrank, F.von P. (1782) Fortsetzung der kritischen Revision des österreichischen Insectenverzeichnisses. *Neues Magazin für die Liebhaber der Entomologie* (ed. J.C. Fuessly), 1(Heft 3), 263–306.
- Schrank, F. von P. (1802) *Fauna Boica. Durchgedachte Geschichte der in Baiern einheimischen und zahmen Thiere. Zweiter Band. Zweite Abtheilung*. Bey Johann Wilhelm Krüll, Ingolstadt, 412 pp.
- Schulz, W.A. (1906) Strandgut. *Spolia Hymenopterologica*, 1906, 76–269.
- Scopoli, I.A. (1763) *Entomologia Carniolica exhibens Insecta Carnioliae indigena et Distributa in Ordines, Genera, Species, Varietates. Methodo Linnaeana*. I.T. Trattner, Vindobonae, [36] pp. + pp. 1–423.
- Serville, A. (1823) Hyménoptères. In: Vieillot, P. Desmarest, A.G. De Blainville, Prévost, C., Serville, A. & Lepelletier Saint-Fargeau (eds), *Faune Française, ou histoire naturelle, générale et particulière, des animaux qui se trouvent en France, Livr. 7 & 8*, Chez Rapet, Paris, pp. 1–96.
- Shahrokhi, M.B. & Zare, A. (1995) The biology of barberry sawfly, *Syrista parreyssi* Spinola (Hymenoptera: Cephidae), in Khorasan province, pp. 270.
- Shahmohammadi, D., Sadeghi, S.E., Melika, G. & Ali, B. (2008) Report of *Tremex fuscicornis* (Hymenoptera: Siricidae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 27(2), 11–12. [In Persian with English summary]
- Shinohara, A. (1997) New or Noteworthy Distribution Records of Six Palaearctic Species of Pamphiliid Sawflies (Hymenoptera). *Bulletin of the National Science Museum, Series A, Zoology*, 23(1), 69–72.
- Shinohara, A. (2002) Systematics of the leaf-rolling or web-spinning sawfly subfamily Pamphiliinae (Hymenoptera): a preliminary overview. pp. 359–438. In: Viitasaary, M. (Ed.), *Sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) I. A review of the suborder, the Western Palaearctic taxa of Xyeloidea and Pamphilioidea*. Tremex, Helsinki.
- Sichel, F.J. (1860) Liste des Hyménoptères Recueillis en Sicile par M. E. Bellier de la Chavignerie. Pendant les mois d'Août à Septembre 1859. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (3), 8(4), 749–764.
- Smith, D.R. (1979) Nearctic sawflies. IV. Allantinae: Adults and larvae (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Technical Bulletin, U.S. Department of Agriculture*, 1595, 1–172.
- Smith, D.R. (1983) The first Record of *Nematus Panzer* from South America: a new species from Argentina (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, 85(2), 260–262.
- Smith, D.R. (1988) A synopsis of the sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) of America south of the United States: introduction, Xyelidae, Pamphiliidae, Cimbicidae, Diprionidae, Xiphydriidae, Siricidae, Orussidae, Cephidae. *Systematic Entomology*, 13, 205–261. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.1988.tb00242.x>
- Smith, D.R. (2003) A Synopsis of the Sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) of America South of the United States: Tenthredinidae (Allantinae). *Journal of Hymenoptera Research*, 12(1), 148–192.
- Smith, F. (1874) Descriptions of new species of Tenthredinidae, Ichneumonidae, Chrysididae, Formicidae &c. of Japan. *Transactions of the*

- Entomological Society of London for the Year, 1874, 373–409.*
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2311.1874.tb00867.x>
- Spinola, M. (1808) *Insectorum liguriae species novae aut rariores, quas in agro Ligustico nuper detexit, descripsit, et iconibus illustravit Maximilianus Spinola, adjecto catalogo specierum auctoribus jam enumeratarum, quae in eadem regione passim occurrunt*. Vol. 2(1)(1807), 2(2–4)(1808), Symptibus Auctoris, Typis Yves Gravier, Genuae, pp. 1–262 + i–v.
- Spinola, M. (1843) Sur quelques Hyménoptères peu connus, recueillis en Espagne, pendant l'année 1842, par M. Victor Ghiliani, voyageur-naturaliste. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (2), 1, 111–162.
- Springate, N.D., Burckhardt, D.H. & Springate, L.S. (2011) New species of Megalodontesidae (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Pamphilioidea) from North Africa and the Middle East. *Entomologist's Record and Journal of Variation*, 123(3), May 2011, 131–144.
- Stein, J.P.E.F. (1876) Einige neue dalmatinische, griechische und kleinasiatische Tenthredinoiden. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 37, 53–61.
- Stein, R.von (1881) Beitrag zur Kenntniss der Nematiden. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 7(4), 60–65.
- Stein, R.von (1885) Tenthredinologische Studien IX. *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 11(8), 113–122.
- Stein, R.von (1886) Tenthredinologische Studien XI. (Schluss). *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 12(3), 33–40.
- Stephens, J.F. (1829) *A Systematic Catalogue of British Insects: being an attempt to arrange all the hitherto discovered indigenous insects in accordance with their natural affinities. Containing also references to every English writer on entomology, etc. Vol. 1*. Published for the Author, by Baldwin & Cradock, London, pp. i–xxxiv + 1–416.
<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.8987>
- Stephens, J.F. (1835) *Illustrations of British Entomology; or, a Synopsis of Indigenous Insects: containing their generic and specific distinctions; with an account of their metamorphosis, times of appearance, localities, food, and economy, as far as practicable. Mandibulata. Vol. 7*. Baldwin & Cradock, London, pp. 1–312.
- Strobl, G. (1901) Hymenopteren aus Ungarn und Siebenbürgen. Gesammelt von Professor Gabriel Strobl und Professor Johann Thalhammer, bestimmt und zusammengestellt von Professor Gabriel Strobl. *Verhandlungen und Mittheilungen des siebenbürgischen Vereins für Naturwissenschaften zu Hermannstadt*, 50[1900], 43–79.
- Taeger, A. (1985) Zur Systematik der Blattwespengattung *Tenthredo* (s. str.) Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Tenthredinidae). *Entomologische Abhandlungen*, 48 [1984] (8), 83–148.
- Taeger, A. (1988a) Zweiter Beitrag zur Systematik der Blattwespengattung *Tenthredo* (s. str.) (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Tenthredinidae). *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 38(1), 103–153.
- Taeger, A. (1988b) Dritter Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Blattwespengattung *Tenthredo* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Symphyta: Tenthredinidae). *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 38(2), 337–359.
- Taeger, A. (1991) Vierter Beitrag zur Systematik der Blattwespengattung *Tenthredo* Linnaeus. Die Untergattung *Zonuledo* Zhelochovtsev, 1988 (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). *Entomofauna. Zeitschrift für Entomologie*, 12(23), 373–398.
- Taeger, A. (1992) Fünfter Beitrag zur Systematik der Blattwespengattung *Tenthredo* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 42 (1), 3–53.
- Taeger, A. (2002) The Megalodontesidae of Europe (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). In: Viitasaari, M. (Ed.), *Sawflies* (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) I. A review of the suborder, the Western Palaearctic taxa of Xyeloidea and Pamphilioidea. Tremex, Helsinki, pp. 461–480.
- Taeger, A., Altenhofer, E., Blank, S.M., Jansen, E., Kraus, M., Pschorn-Walcher, H. & Ritzau, C. (1998) Kommentare zur Biologie, Verbreitung und Gefährdung der Pflanzenwespen Deutschlands (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). In: Taeger, A., Blank, S.M. (Eds.), *Pflanzenwespen Deutschlands* (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). *Kommentierte Bestandsaufnahme*. Goecke & Evers, Kelttern, pp. 49–135.

- Taeger, A. & Blank, S.M. (2011) ECatSym—Electronic World Catalog of Symphyta (Insecta: Hymenoptera). Program version 3.10, data version 38 (07.12.2011). Digital Entomological Information, Müncheberg. Available from <http://www.sdei.de/ecatsym/index.html> (accessed 3 January 2013).
- Taeger, A., Blank, S.M. & Liston, A.D. (2010) World Catalog of Symphyta (Hymenoptera). *Zootaxa*, 2580, 1–1064.
- Takeuchi, K. (1931) A list of the Japanese Crabronidae (Cimbicidae) with description of four new species. *The Transactions of the Kansai Entomological Society*, 2, 13–26.
- Thomson, C.G. (1863) Entomologiska bidrag. *Öfversigt af Kongliga Vetenskaps-Akademiens förhandlingar*, 19[1862](10), 611–639.
- Thomson, C.G. (1870) Öfversigt af Sveriges Tenthrediner. *Opuscula Entomologica*. Edidit C. G. Thomson, 2, 261–304.
- Thomson, C.G. (1871) *Hymenoptera Scandinaviae (Tenthredo et Sirex Lin.)*. H. Olsson, Lundae, 1, 1–342.
- Thomson, C.G. (1888) XXXVII. Bidrag till Sveriges insectfauna. *Opuscula Entomologica*. Edidit C. G. Thomson, 12, 1202–1265.
- Thunberg, C.P. (1789) *D. D. Museum Naturalium Academiae Upsaliensis. Cujus partem Septimam. Consensu exp. Fac. Med. Upsal. praeside Carol. Pet. Thunberg, Publico examini subjicit Johannes Branzell Verb. div. min. Vermelandus. J. Edman, Upsalia*, [1] p.
- Tischbein (1846) Verzeichniss der in den Fürstenthümern Lübeck und Birkenfeld von mir bisher aufgefundenen Blattwespen. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 7, 75–80, 113–115.
- Tischbein (1852a) Wissenschaftliche Mitteilungen. Hymenopterologische Beiträge. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 13, 137–142.
- Tischbein (1852b) Hymenopterologische Beiträge. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*, 13(4), 103–108.
- Tischbein (1852c) Hymenopterologische Beiträge. *Entomologische Zeitung (Stettin)*. 13(5), 137–140.
- Togashi, I. (1997) Korean sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) collected by Mr. T. Tano and Mrs C. Nozaka in 1985 and 1986. *Bulletin of the Biogeographical Society of Japan*, 52(2), 29–31.
- Uchida, T. (1927) Beitrag zur Kenntnis der japanischen Cimbex- und Agenocimbex-Arten (Hym.). *Insecta Matsumurana*, 2(3), 155–162.
- Ushinskij, A.V. (1936) Materialy k faune Tenthredinodea Turkmenskoj SSR. *Byulleten turkmenskoy zoologicheskoy stantsii, Ashkhabad and Baku*, 1, 103–115.
- Vallot, J.N. (1836) Observations Entomologiques. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences, Arts et Belles-Lettres de Dijon*, 1836, 206–255.
- Vallot, J.N. (1845) Sur les tenthredes de la vigne. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences, Arts et Belles-Lettres de Dijon*, 1843–1844(Partie des Sciences), 50–52.
- Vallot, J.N. (1848) Observations d'histoire naturelle. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences, Arts et Belles-Lettres de Dijon*, 1847–1848(Partie des Sciences), 179–217.
- Vassilev, I.B. (1969) Neue Blattwespenart *Amasis* Leach. (Cimbicidae: Hymenoptera) aus Bulgarien. *Doklady Bolgarskoj Akademii Nauk*, 22(6), 695–696.
- Villers, C.J. de (1789) *Caroli Linnaei entomologia, faunae suecicae descriptionibus aucta; D. D. Scopoli, Geoffroy, De Geer, Fabricii, Schrank etc. speciebus vel in Systemate non enumeratis, vel nuperrime detectis, vel speciebus Galliae australis locupletata, generum specierumque rariorum iconibusornata; Curante et augente Carolo de Villers; Vol. 3. Piestre et Delamolliere, Lugduni*, XXIV + 657 pp.
- Vollenhoven, S.S.C. van (1858a) Naamlijst van nederlandsche vliesvleugelige Insekten, Beschrijving der nieuwe soorten. *Bouwstoffen voor eene Fauna van Nederland, onder medewerking van onderschiedene geleerden en beoffenaars der dierkunde*, 2, 276–283.
- Vollenhoven, S.S.C. van (1858b) De inlandsche bladwespen in hare gedaanteverwisselingen en levenswijze beschreven. *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie*, 1, 171–194.
- Vollenhoven, S.S.C. van (1871) De inlandsche bladwespen in hare gedaantewisseling en levenswijze beschreven. *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie*, 14, 237–254 [reprint paginated 1–18].

- Vollenhoven, S.S.C. van (1873) De inlandsche bladwespen in hare gedaantewisseling en levenswijze beschreven. *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie*, 16[1872], 1–15 [reprint paginated 1–15].
- Vollenhoven, S.S.C. van (1878) Espèces nouvelles ou peu connues d'Hyménoptères térébrants. *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie*, 21(3), 153–177.
- Walsh, B.D. (1866) On the Insects, coleopterous, hymenopterous and dipterous, inhabiting the Galls of certain species of Willow. — Part 2d and last. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Philadelphia*, 6, 223–288.
- Wei, M. (2008) On the genus *Syrista* Konow, with the description of a new species from China (Hymenoptera: Cephidae). *Entomological News*, 118(5), 450–458.
[https://doi.org/10.3157/0013-872X\(2007\)118\[450:OTGSKW\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.3157/0013-872X(2007)118[450:OTGSKW]2.0.CO;2)
- Wei, M. & Smith, D.R. (2010) Review of *Syrista* Konow (Hymenoptera: Cephidae). *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, 112(2), 302–316.
<https://doi.org/10.4289/0013-8797-112.2.302>
- Weldon, G.P. (1907) Tenthredinidae of Colorado. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 39(9), 295–304.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent39295-9>
- Zaddach, G. (1859) Beschreibung neuer oder wenig bekannter Blattwespen aus dem Gebiet der preussischen Fauna. In: *Zur öffentlichen Prüfung der Schüler des Königlichen Friedrichs-Collegiums am Montag den 3. und am Dienstag den 4. October 1859*, Schultzche Hofbuchdruckerei, Königsberg in Pr., pp. 3–40.
- Zaddach, G. (1863) Beobachtungen über die Arten der Blatt- und Holzwespen von C. G. A. Brischke erstem Lehrer am Spend- und Waisenhaus zu Danzig und Dr. Gustav Zaddach, Professor in Königsberg, mitgeteilt von Zaddach. *Schriften der physikalisch-ökonomischen Gesellschaft zu Königsberg*, 3[1862], 204–278 (Sep. 3–77).
- Zaddach, G. (1866) Beobachtungen über die Arten der Blatt- und Holzwespen von C. G. A. Brischke Hauptlehrer an der altstädtischen evangelischen Knabenschule in Danzig und Dr. Gustav Zaddach, Professor in Königsberg, mitgeteilt von Zaddach. [Dritte Abhandlung] *Lydidae. Schriften der physikalisch-ökonomischen Gesellschaft zu Königsberg*, 6[1865], 104–203.
- Zetterstedt, J.W. (1838) Ordo IV. Hymenoptera. In: Zetterstedt, J.W., *Insecta Lapponica descripta. Sectio Secunda*. L. Voss, Lipsiae, pp. 326–358.
- Zhelochovtsev, A. (1927) Neue Tenthredinoidea aus Asien (Hym.). *Entomologische Mitteilungen*, 16(1), 81–83.
- Zhelochovtsev, A.N. (1976) Materialy po faune pililshnikov i rogochvostov srednej Asii, I. *Sbornik trudov Zoologitscheskogo Muzeja MGU*, 15, 3–73.
- Zhelochovtsev, A.N. & Zinovjev, A.G. (1993 [1988]) Hymenoptera Part VI Symphyta. [Translation of the book from 1988]. In: Medvedev, G.S. (ed.): *Keys to the Insects of the European Part of the USSR*. [Opredelitel' Nasekomykh Evropeiskoi Chasti SSSR, Tom III, Pereponchatokrylye, Shestaia Chast']. Amerind Publ. Co. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi 3(6), 1–387.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1937a) Beitrag zur Biologie des *Emphytus* Klg. (*Allantus* Pz. u. Jur.) *balteatus* Klg. und Beschreibung des unbekanntes Männchens. *Festschrift zum 60. Geburtstage von Professor Dr. Embrik Strand*, 2, 638–647.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1937b) Neue oder wenig bekannte Tenthrediniden (Hym.) aus dem Naturhistorischen Museum in Wien. *Festschrift zum 60. Geburtstage von Professor Dr. Embrik Strand*, 3, 335–350.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1937c) Ein Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Blattwespen. *Festschrift zum 60. Geburtstage von Professor Dr. Embrik Strand*, 3, 350–355.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1949) Ein Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Tenthrediniden. (Hym.). *Mitteilungen der Münchner Entomologischen Gesellschaft*, 35–39[1945–1949], 283–290.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1953) Tenthrediniden aus der Zoologischen Staatssammlung in München. *Mitteilungen der Münchner Entomologischen Gesellschaft*, 43, 234–238.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1954) Zur Wespenfauna der Pfalz. II. Teil: Blatt-, Holz- und Halmwespen. *Mitteilungen der Pollichia, des Pfälzischen Vereins für Naturkunde und Naturschutz III. Reihe*, 2, 119–194.
- Zirngiebl, L. (1956) Blattwespen aus Iran. *Mitteilungen der Münchner Entomologischen Gesellschaft*, 46, 322–326.

لیست زنبورهای تخم‌ریز اره‌ای (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) در ایران

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چکیده: لیست کامل و به‌روز شده از زنبورهای تخم‌ریز اره‌ای (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) ارائه شده است. این لیست شامل ۱۷۸ گونه متعلق به ۶۰ جنس و ۹ خانواده می‌باشد. خانواده‌ی Tenthredinidae دارای بیشترین غنای گونه‌ای (با ۱۳۱ گونه)، و پس از آن Argidae (۱۸ گونه)، Cephidae (۹ گونه)، Megalodontesidae (۷ گونه)، Cimbicidae (۴ گونه)، Pamphiliidae (۳ گونه)، و خانواده‌های Orussidae، Siricidae و Xiphydriidae (۲ گونه) قرار گرفته‌اند. همچنین جنس *Tenthredo* با ۲۳ گونه دارای بیشترین غنای گونه‌ای و پس از آن *Macrophya* از خانواده‌ی Tenthredinidae با ۱۷ گونه و *Arge* از خانواده‌ی Argidae با ۱۲ گونه دارای بیشترین گونه در بین سایر جنس‌های این زیرراسته می‌باشند. پراکنش، هم‌نام‌ها و میزبان‌های گیاهی لاروهای گونه‌های گزارش شده از ایران ارائه شده است.

واژگان کلیدی: بال‌غشاییان، زنبورهای تخم‌ریز اره‌ای، چک‌لیست، پراکنش، ایران.